

Manual on ecotourism best practices & Code of conduct for tour operators

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1. Introduction

Coastal ecosystems are among the most productive ecosystems in the world. Nature-based tourism (i.e. the activities involved should focus predominantly on the natural environment) has become more important in terms of size and contribution to national economies, as well as to the well-being of local communities. However, in the absence of adequate controls, the growth of unplanned tourism can cause environmental degradation and social and cultural conflicts which compromise the long-term sustainability of the tourism sector.

Defining ecotourism and marine ecotourism is not a simple process. It has to take into consideration both marine nature-based tourism and sustainable marine tourism. Ecotourism is now defined as “responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment, sustains the well-being of the local people, and involves interpretation and education” (The International Ecotourism Society, www.ecotourism.org). Education is meant to be inclusive of both staff and guests.

Ecotourism could be seen as an alternative form of tourism. It can generally be described as a minimal impact, interpretative tourism in which conservation, understanding and appreciation of the environment and the cultures visited are sought. It entails travel to natural areas with the ecotourist involved in the ecotourism experience that expresses an explicit motivation to satisfy the need for education and environmental, social and / or cultural awareness through the visit and experience of the natural area. Ecotourism’s focus on the natural environment has, in recent years, facilitated its evolution into a catchphrase that encompasses numerous tourism forms including ‘nature tourism,’ ‘wilderness tourism,’ ‘low impact

tourism,’ and ‘sustainable tourism’ to name a few. These diverse forms of tourism all focus on the natural environment to some extent and, although closely aligned and related to ecotourism, need to be distinguished from ecotourism as there are a number of dimensions to nature-based tourism. Those two main paradigms have emerged here, ecotourism, which is a demand-driven concept limited to nature-based tourism; and sustainable tourism, which is a supply-sided view characterized by industry regulations. Ecotourism, therefore, has the potential to be a means to improve understanding of environmental values, support for local communities' economies and a sense of cultural identity, as well as an activity that arose due to a fundamental change in the way nature, is seen by society.

The book is divided in three main section: the first provide an overview of the on-the water tourism in the Vlora region with the approach of the diagnostic cartography; the second is a manual on the ecotourism best practices and the third is the code of conduct. The manual of ecotourism best practices is divided in five sections: status of ecotourism, guidelines for sustainable tourism, conservation, participation and awareness, monitoring and evaluation, and citizen science as monitoring tool. In the code of conduct chapter, there are three sections, namely: sustainable practices for on the water tourism, ecotourism guidelines for travellers and accrediting. For each chapter, case studies and/or examples are provided.

2. Marine conservation and on-the-water tourism in the Vlorë region: an overview

The Karaburun Peninsula is a strip of land that goes from Orikum to the sea. It hosts cliffs, caves and beaches of rare beauty. The Karaburun promontory has peaks that exceed 1000 m in height, it is very green and has cliffs overlooking the sea, as well as being scattered with bays. The island of Sazan (Fig. 2.1) has been open to tour boats since 2015. It is an island characterised by crystal clear waters and beautiful beaches.

Albania's Karaburun-Sazan Marine Protected Area (hereafter, K-S MPA) was established in 2010 as a National Marine Park. The MPA, with a total surface of 12,750 ha, stretches 1 nm along the Western and Eastern coast of the Karaburun Peninsula and 1 nm around Sazan Island, excluding the military port.

MPAs represent core attractions for sustainable tourism. K-S MPA being characterised with pristine landscapes, high-quality habitats and biodiversity, both on land and in the sea, history and cultural heritage, could be seen as a vehicle for sustainable tourism. That could generate positive economic impacts and benefits to the local population, and provide a strong potential for conservation actions.

Fig. 2.1 Sazan Island (Photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

One of the main objectives of marine spatial planning is to promote sustainable use of marine resources without jeopardizing biodiversity and habitats. Developing marine spatial plans requires knowledge of the composition and distribution of benthic communities, the characteristics of the natural state, the impacts of different human activities and the level of protection in use. Diagnostic cartography consists in the cartographic representation of a set of synthetic indicators for the evaluation of the territory to be managed, thus it could allow a comparison of the expected effects of different management solutions on coastal ecosystem (Parravicini et al. 2012). In 1992, Agenda 21 enunciated the need for diagnostic tools for the coastal zone, which including the sustainable development of coastal and marine areas (Bianchi et al. 2012).

Three thematic maps are used for the first level of the environmental characterization, and five for the evaluation. The maps for environmental characterization are: MPA zonation and touristic activities, legislative constrain, and marine habitats. The maps for environmental evaluation are: environmental value, cumulative impact, cumulative protection, weighted environmental risk and weighted management needs. The environmental characterization maps allow identifying coastal marine areas in which some recreational and/or professional activities are not authorized or are limited. While the maps on environmental assessment are useful tools for managers to achieve sustainable development.

2.1 Environmental characterization maps

Management zone and activities map

The Karaburun-Sazan MPA is divided into four zones with different levels of legal protection and management measures (Fig 4.1 and Fig. 4.2): (1) the core zone (CZ); (2) the effective management zone (EMZ); (3) the sustainable development zone (SDZ); and (4) the recreation zone (RZ). The CZ is a fully protected zone (no-take and no entry except for scientific research and surveillance). Within the EMZ, several activities are permitted but strictly regulated such as scientific research and monitoring, waste removal, diving, boating excursions, sailing and mooring, kayaking, water sports, visits, and wildlife watching. In the RZ and SDZ, sailing, swimming, snorkelling, anchoring, mooring, kayaking, water sports, and visiting are allowed. Small-scale fishery activities (mainly trammel nets and longlines) are allowed and regulated and authorised by the Regional Administration for Protected Areas. Within the SDZ, only non-motor water sports are permitted (Bakiu et al. 2018).

The stretch of coast that includes the K-S MPA is the site of a number of human settlements and activities, such as cities, ports, fish farms, tourism operations, and a number of large-scale fisheries and small-scale fisheries (Fig. 2.2 and Fig. 2.3). Maps were prepared using the free and open-source geographic information system QGIS ver. 3.4 (qgis.org).

Fig. 2.2 Main commercial activities and K-S MPA management zones at Vlorë province, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Fig. 2.3 Main commercial activities and K-S MPA management zones at Vlorë province, close up of Vlorë bay, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Restrictions map

Several restrictions were also enforced in the Vlorë bay, such as non-authorized use of bottom, gill nets and purse seine, of hydraulic dredges, of towered gear, and the presence of no-fishing zones (Fig. 2.4 and Fig. 2.5).

Fig. 2.4 Activities restrictions at Vlorë province, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Fig. 2.5 Activities restrictions at Vlorë province, close up of Vlorë bay, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Habitat map

The habitat maps provide information on the main typology of habitat in the Vlora bay. These kinds of maps are important for point out the main habitats which require protections, such as coralligenous habitats, *Posidonia oceanica* and *Cymodocea nodosa* meadows (Fig. 2.6 and Fig. 2.7).

Fig. 2.6 Main marine habitats at Vlore province, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Fig. 2.7 Main marine habitats at Vlorë province, close up of Vlorë bay, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

2.2. Evaluation maps

To produce the environmental evaluation maps, the marine territory was divided into territorial units (TU), a 1 km grid. Each cell was scored according to the sum of the main environmental value, impact, protection, environmental risk and management level in that cell, respectively. The final territorial scores of the cells are then reported in classes obtained by dividing them into quintiles. A colour was assigned to each class using red, orange, yellow, light green and dark green scale. More data distributed equally along the coast would allow more accurate maps. Spatial analysis and mapping were done using the free and open-source geographic information system QGIS ver. 3.4 (qgis.org).

Environmental value map

The map of the environmental value was obtained taking into consideration the type of habitat present (e.g. *Posidonia oceanica* meadow, which are considered a priority habitat according to the EU Habitats Directive or the coralligenous habitats). For example, the coralligenous mesophotic biogenic reefs (*sensu* Ballesteros 2006) are among the most important marine benthic subtidal habitats in the Mediterranean Sea because of their high species diversity, structural and functional complexity (see Ballesteros 2006, Ingrosso et al. 2018 and references therein). K-S MPA is characterised by coralligenous and pre-coralligenous habitats along the coasts (Kashta et al. 2010, Andromede Oceanology 2016, Shkurti 2019).

The environmental value is very high in the northeast side of the island of Sazan, mainly due to the presence of the *Posidonia* meadow. Furthermore, it is also very high and high in the northern part of the Karaburun Peninsula.

This value is due to the presence of caves and coralligenous habitats, which are very fragile ecosystems, (Fig. 2.8 and Fig. 2.9).

Fig. 2.8 Environmental values map at Vlorë province, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Fig. 2.9 Environmental values map at Vlorë province, close up of Vlorë bay, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Cumulative impact map

The impacts that were considered to produce the cumulative impact map were: tourist boat routes, diving and anchoring points, the presence of restaurants or camping sites, fish farm areas and water pollution derived from the punctual values of faecal coliforms and *Escherichia coli* of the year 2018.

Sazan Island shows very low to low cumulative impacts values, indicating that anthropogenic pressures in the area are low or absent. The Karaburun Peninsula is in good condition, but with cumulative impact values ranging from high to very high in some areas, generally near restaurants, diving spots, along tour boat routes and close to fish farms. Vlora bay has on average low and moderate cumulative impacts (Fig. 2.10 and Fig. 2.11).

Fig. 2.10 Cumulative impacts map at Vlorë province, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Fig. 2.11 Cumulative impacts map at Vlorë province, close up of Vlorë bay, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Cumulative protection map

The cumulative protection map represents the degree of protection present in the area, obtained by considering the zoning of the MPA and the restrictions on the various recreational and/or professional activities.

Protection around the island of Sazan is very high, mainly due to the many restrictions of on-the-water activities. The west side of the Karaburun Peninsula also has very high protection. This value is partly due to the restrictions imposed by the zoning of protected marine areas, to the ban on fishing and to not be an area very frequented by recreational and professional activities, being often an area characterized by unfavourable marine weather conditions (Fig. 2.12 and Fig. 2.13).

Fig. 2.12 Cumulative protection map at Vlore province, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Fig. 2.13 Cumulative protection map at Vlorë province, close up of Vlorë bay, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Environmental risk map

The environmental risk map is weighted on the results obtained in the environmental value and cumulative impacts maps. The environmental risk map shows the areas most sensitive to anthropogenic impact. In particular, very sensitive and fragile habitats because characterized by endangered species or by particular environmental conditions (such as caves, seagrass meadows or coralligenous habitats), if combined with intense human activities, will show high values of environmental risk. Here is the case Haxhi Ali cave, which is the most famous cave on the Karaburun Peninsula and a must-see for the boat trip. The value of environmental risk obtained is very high (Fig. 2.14 and Fig. 2.15). Caves are fragile habitats, which need conservation measures to preserve them (Bussotti et al. 2006, Di Franco et al. 2010, Guarnieri et al. 2012, Dimarchopoulou et al. 2018, Montefalcone et al. 2018). The need for management and regulatory plan to regulate entry into the cave for both boats and snorkelers is important. Some suggestions made are the creation of a timetable for boats to avoid the congestion of tourists at the same moment, the construction of a floating pier to prevent the direct entry of boats, and entry-ticket to the cave.

Fig. 2.14 Environmental risk map at Vlorë province, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Fig. 2.15 Environmental risk map at Vlorë province, close up of Vlorë bay, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Management needs map

The management needs map is weighted based on the results obtained in the cumulative protection and environmental risk maps. Combining sensitivity to environmental risk with the protection currently applied in the various areas, the map indicates the areas that need management interventions. This map represents an important tool for efficient management because clearly shows which areas require more urgent action by the competent authorities (Fig. 2.16 and Fig. 2.17). Furthermore, for areas that have a very high need for managerial intervention, the map annotates the main anthropic pressures on which to intervene: over-tourism in caves and coralligenous habitats (mainly in the northern side of Karaburun Peninsula), marine traffic and anchoring on seagrass meadows (mainly in front of Radhima), pollution risk due to sewage and oil spills (mainly in front of Vlora port), and illegal and destructive fishing (mainly in the east side of the Karaburun Peninsula; Fig. 2.16 and Fig. 2.17). This is a preliminary map based on current knowledge, the areas and anthropic pressures indicated are just probable. Further studies are needed to obtain more accurate and precise results.

Fig. 2.16 Management needs map at Vlorë province, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

Fig. 2.17 Management needs map at Vlorë province, close up of Vlorë bay, Projection UTM34N, WGS84 datum (source: UNDP)

3. Manual on ecotourism best practices

3.1 Status of ecotourism

Tourism is considered by the United Nation World Trade Organisation (UNWTO 2016) as key to economic development and the human well being of a nation and can be community based, nature based (Orams 1996, Neto 2003, Biggs et al. 2012), or culture and heritage based (Dowling 2011). The year 2017 was designed by the UNWTO as the International Year of Sustainable Tourism for Development. According to the UNWTO, the sustainable tourism is: “Tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities” (UNWTO 2005). It involves a process, which meets the needs of tourists and host communities while protecting and enhancing needs in the future.

There is a broad consensus that tourism development should be sustainable; however, the problem is of how to manage tourism growth to achieve this object. Tourism is one of the world's largest and fastest-growing industries, and when not well managed will place high stress on the environment and local cultures. Sustainable tourism is sensitive to these dangers and seeks to protect the pristine tourist destinations and the local culture. There are several ways to reduce the impact of tourism and approach the problem more sustainably:

- Respecting and supporting the integrity of local cultures by favouring businesses which conserve cultural heritage and traditional values

- Conserving resources by seeking out environmentally conscious businesses

The relationship between tourism and sustainable development is based on three main pillars (UNWTO 2005):

- The interaction among tourists, the local communities and the environment;
- The increasing awareness of the visitors about environmental issues and different cultures;
- The dependency of the tourist sector on being in a place of intact and clean environments, attractive natural areas, authentic historical and cultural traditions, and welcoming hosts.

Tourism can be a positive force for sustainable development by providing direct income and opportunities for activities development and employment creation. However, if political and management actions do not sustain tourism, by increasing the pressure on the environment, it could be a cause of environmental degradation.

Nowadays, responsible tourism is seen as a pathway to sustainable tourism. Responsible tourism and sustainable tourism have the same goal: sustainable development. The pillars of responsible tourism are therefore the same as those of sustainable tourism – environmental integrity, social justice and economic development. The emphasis on responsibility means that everyone involved in tourism (government, operators, transport operators, NGOs, tourists, local communities, industry associations) is

responsible for achieving the goals set. Stakeholders, both individuals and organisations, play a crucial role in pursuing sustainable tourism (Aas et al. 2005).

The Global Sustainable Tourism Council (GSTC) is the international body for promoting sustainable tourism practices, fostering the adoption of universal sustainable tourism principles and building demand for sustainable travel.

The governments are essential players in defining sustainable tourism as well. Indeed, they set the national strategy of sustainable tourism; they need to take into account the carrying capacity of the area of interest. This is the capacity of visitors in an area that can sustainably tolerate without damaging the environment or culture of the surrounding area. The carrying capacity can be altered and revised in time and with changing perceptions and values.

Non-governmental organisations are one of the stakeholders in advancing sustainable tourism. Their roles can range from spearheading sustainable tourism practices to doing research.

Local communities benefit from sustainable tourism through income increasing, job creation, and infrastructure development. Tourism revenues bring economic growth to nature-based tourist destinations, which can raise the standard of living in destination communities. Moreover, the increase in tourism revenue to an area acts as a driver for the development of infrastructure. As tourist demands growth in a destination, more infrastructures are needed to support the needs of both the tourism industry and the local community (Walker and Moscardo 2014, Moscardo et al. 2017).

The environmental sustainability focuses on the overall viability and health of ecological systems. Natural resource degradation, pollution, and loss of biodiversity are detrimental because they increase vulnerability, undermine system health, and reduce resilience (Bellan and Bellan-Santini 2001, Shaalan 2005, Paoli et al. 2013, Mendoza-Gonzalez et al. 2018).

Many coastal areas are experiencing particular pressure from growing numbers of tourists. The coastal zone is the transition zone between the terrestrial and aquatic environment of an ocean, a gulf, a sea or a large lake and includes all the transitional habitats. The growing presence of tourist activities, the concentration of pollutants, the modification of the profile of the coast due to urbanisation interventions, can alter the balance of the biotic and abiotic components. Coastal areas are often the first environments to experience the detrimental impacts of tourism. Planning and management controls can reduce the impact on coastal environments and ensure that investment in tourism products supports sustainable coastal tourism (Tonin 2018).

Nature-based tourism involving unique features of the natural environment has been popularized in many developed and developing countries around the world. In particular, marine and coastal tourism has been identified as one of the promising areas for development worldwide (Hall and Page 2009).

Nature-based tourism has the potential to improve the conservation of biodiversity by providing alternative and non-destructive sources of livelihood to local populations (Neto 2003, Liu et al. 2012). A well-managed ecotourism could bring socio-economic benefits (e.g. income, employment, positive attitudes towards conservation) to host community and be able to attract private investments for the nature conservation. Country-specific

studies on sea turtles, for example, show that conservation programs all around the world, such as the Brazilian Sea Turtle Conservation Program (TAMAR, <http://www.tamar.org.br/> ; Marcovaldi and dei Marcovaldi 1999), Sea Turtle Conservation Volunteer Project in Greece (<https://www.archelon.gr/eng/volunt.php>), Playa Tortuga Conservation Program in Costa Rica (<https://reservaplayatortuga.org/>), have been successful in building a win-win situation by creating economic benefits (i.e. employment and income) and by conserving sea turtles through the development of ecotourism and community participation local (Marcovaldi and dei Marcovaldi 1999, Al Busaidi et al. 2019).

Ecotourism raises environmental awareness and disseminates an understanding of the good environmental practices with advantages to the business.

However, tourism, if not well-managed could have adverse effects. There are several examples of marine tourist destinations becoming polluted, degraded, and congested by mass-market travel (Al Busaidi et al. 2019). One way of attempting to deal with such problems of increasing environmental degradation of the natural environment is by ‘environmental best practice.’

Best practice involves seeking excellence, embracing innovations, avoiding waste, and focusing on outcomes that are in the community interest (Wearing and Neil 2009). It implies managing change and continual improvement, and in this way, it encompasses all levels of an organization. Examples of marine best practices include aiming to conserve the marine environment, increase customer service or improvements in collaboration with other marine-related services (Wearing and Neil 2009).

Best practice can be associated with ecotourism, particularly in regard to the increasing levels of environmental concern and awareness worldwide. An example of this is the IUCN World Commission on Protected Areas (WCPA) Best Practice Guidelines series. In “Tourism and visitor management in protected areas” (Leung et al. 2018), the guidelines provide guidance on key issues to help managers achieve sustainable tourism in protected areas.

Numerous forms of environmental -marine- best practices are currently used by ecotourism operators, ranging from the issue of licenses and permits for accessing wild natural areas to the development of codes of practice for tourists, operators, and managers.

CASE STUDY: Great Barrier Reef Marine Park

The Great Barrier Reef Marine Park is now the largest protected sea area in the world after the Australian Government increased the areas protected from extractive activities (such as fishing and sand mining) from 4.6% to 33.3%.

The Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority is Australia's key management agency for the Great Barrier Reef, and works with government, industry and community to protect the area. The Marine Park is widely recognised as one of the best managed marine-protected areas in the world. Its management involves ensuring environmental protection while allowing for national, state and community interests in sustainable use. A range of regulatory tools allows in managing multiple activities in the Marine Park, including the Zoning Plan, plans of management, permits, and policies, as well as a range of partnerships and management arrangements (Fig. 3.1). The Great Barrier Marine Park Zoning Plan 2003 superseded all previous zoning plans, coming into effect on 1 July 2004.

Fig. 3.1 Great Barrier Reef Marine Park, Cairns zoning map (source: <http://elibrary.gbrmpa.gov.au>)

That plan provides for a range of ecologically sustainable recreational, commercial and research opportunities and for the continuation of traditional activities. Zoning helps to manage and protect the values of the Marine Park that people enjoy. Each zone has different rules for the activities that are allowed, the activities that are prohibited, and the activities that require a permit. There are eight different types of zones that apply to the entire Great Barrier Reef Marine Park:

- General Use (Light Blue)
- Habitat Protection (Dark Blue)
- Conservation Park (Yellow)
- Marine National Park (Green).
- Preservation (Pink)

-
- Scientific Research (Orange)
 - Buffer (Olive Green)
 - Commonwealth Island Zones

As an example, the Marine National Park (Green) Zone is a 'no-take' area, and extractive activities like fishing or collecting are not allowed without a permit. Anyone can enter the Green Zone and participate in activities such as boating, swimming, snorkelling and sailing (Fig. 3.2).

Zones may also place restrictions on how some activities are conducted (Fig. 3.3).

Fig. 3.2 An infographic showing useful information about green zones in the Great Barrier Reef (source: Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority, <http://hdl.handle.net/11017/3393>)

SPEARFISHING

IN THE WHITSUNDAYS?

The Whitsundays is one of the Great Barrier Reef's most highly visited regions, with the greatest concentration of users. To help protect this iconic area, there are special rules in place for spearfishing.

Where is spearfishing allowed in the Whitsunday Planning Area?

To make sure you know where you are allowed to spearfish, please refer to the map on the back of this page.

For ease of understanding, this map combines the rules for Marine Parks zoning, the Public Appreciation Special Management Area and Queensland Fisheries.

For more detailed information, see the Whitsundays Zoning Map 10, or visit www.gbrmpa.gov.au.

Responsible Reef practices

- Spear only what you need
- Do not pursue a fish if you are unsure of its identity or size
- Do not anchor on coral
- Avoid taking plant-eating fish like parrotfish, which remove algae and provide space for new corals to grow

Rules for spearfishing

When you spearfish on the Great Barrier Reef, you can use a snorkel when using a spear or spear gun.

You cannot use: a powerhead or other firearm, a light, scuba or other underwater breathing apparatus.

Note: Fishers using spear guns cannot have a loaded spear gun out of the water.

Australian Government
Great Barrier Reef
Marine Park Authority

Queensland Government

Be crocwise in and around crocodile habitat.

#lovethereef

For further information contact:
Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority
(07) 4750 0700
www.gbrmpa.gov.au

Current as at September 2017

Fig. 3.3 Year 2019 spearfish regulation at Whitsunday, Great Barrier Reef Marine Park, Australia, including responsible reef practices (source: Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority, <http://hdl.handle.net/11017/3252>)

Furthermore, to implement the conservation and sustainable use of the Marine Park, the Australian and Queensland governments are working on the Reef 2050 Long-Term Sustainability Plan (Reef 2050 Plan, <http://www.gbrmpa.gov.au/our-work/reef-strategies/reef-2050>), which provides an overarching strategy for managing the Great Barrier Reef — it coordinates actions and guides adaptive management to 2050.

The plan outlines management measures for 35 years, including clear actions, targets, objectives and outcomes to drive short-term and long-term management of the Great Barrier Reef.

CASE STUDY: Fishing tourism

Fishing tourism or pescaturism is a relatively new development in sustainable tourism. In Italy, it establishes itself in the early 90s in Italy. It consists of a day trip by a fishing boat with local fishermen who bring tourists on board. Tourists take part in fishing operations by throwing and pulling nets and performing other activities, such as eating fish caught onboard and visiting fishing villages. Fishing tourism has involved an increasing number of tourists and has managed to create potential from coastal areas, embracing the fishing industry, landscape, culture, and local economic activities. This potential is able to attract tourists and generate revenue through a process of more sustainable exploitation of local resources.

Through this tourist activity, the conditions could be created for a common vision between tourists and the local population. The latter has a greater incentive to preserve the environment in which they live: in terms of environmental, economic, and social goods, defending them from the negative impacts that may derive from the development of tourism. Tourists, on the other hand, have the opportunity to get to know the culture of an area, by participating directly in an activity, such as traditional fishing practiced.

A research conducted by Lai et al. 2016 has shown a high level of satisfaction with regards to fishing tourism in Italy. A successful fishing tourism service could attract tourists, generating income opportunities through a process of more sustainable exploitation of the sea and internal local resources. Therefore, this sustainable recreational experience could help preserve coastal areas and fishing (Lai et al. 2016).

3.2 Guidelines for sustainable tourism

Ecotourism can be regulated and controlled on a sustainable level. Wanting to protect those areas still intact and which could obtain a future ecological and economic advantage by remaining such (Foran 2007), ecotourism is a supply-driven approach, which involves determining the number of visitors based on the capacity of the environment rather than the demand for it.

Ecotourism is an alternative to mass tourism due to the minimisation of the environmental impacts that derive from it. However, the environmental effects caused by overcrowding, excessive development, unregulated recreational activities, pollution, wildlife disturbances and vehicle use are more serious for ecotourism than mass tourism (McNeely and Thorsell 1989). Ecotourism depends on intact natural environments and is concentrated in ecologically sensitive areas. Without regulations, planning best practices guidelines and appropriate codes of conduct, ecological degradation problems can be intensified with the development of ecotourism (Isaacs 2000, Wearing and Neil 2009, Gladstone et al. 2013).

The American Society of Travel Agents (ASTA, www.asta.org) is the world's largest association of travel professionals. Aiming to encourage environmentally responsible travel, ASTA delineated "The Commandments of Ecotourism":

1. Respect the frailty of the earth. Unique and beautiful destinations may not be here for future generations to enjoy unless all are willing to help in its preservation.
2. Patronize those (hotels, airlines, resorts, cruise lines, tour operators and suppliers) who advance energy conservation; promote water and air quality; provide recycling; manage waste

and toxic materials safely for people and the environment; practice noise abatement; encourages community involvement; and provides experienced, well-trained staff dedicated to strong principles of conservation.

3. Learn about and support conservation-oriented programs and organizations working to preserve the environment and the local culture. Consider a volunteer vacation where you could volunteer to help the local community during a portion of your vacation.
4. Walk or utilize environmentally sound methods of transportation whenever possible.
5. Encourage drivers of public vehicles to stop engines when parked and not idle.
6. Leave only footprints. Take only photographs. No graffiti! No litter! Do not take away "souvenirs" from historical sites and natural areas.
7. To make your travels more meaningful educate yourself about the geography, customs, manners and cultures of the region you visit. Take time to listen to the people. Encourage local conservation efforts.
8. Respect the privacy and dignity of others. Inquire before photographing people.
9. Do not buy products made from endangered plants or animals, such as ivory, tortoise shell, animal skins, and feathers.
10. Always follow designated trails. Do not disturb animals, plants or their natural habitats.

An example that visually summarizes the dichotomy between who is a tourist who is a traveler, incorporating the principles outlined by ASTA, is that provided by Land of Travel (Fig. 3.4).

Tourist	vs.	Traveler
OBSERVES Just there to look around and see the notable "must sees"		EXPERIENCES Immerses themselves in the culture
STICKS OUT Separates themselves from the people and the local culture		BLENDS IN Makes friends and connections with the locals
COMPLAINS Constantly makes comparisons between here and home		CURIOUS Asks questions and explore with an open mind
OBLIVIOUS Doesn't pay attention to people or surroundings		SENSITIVE Aware and respectful of cultural norms
RESULT A nice tan and a thinner wallet		GOAL Values are shaped and lifetime experience is gained
SOUVENIR An overpriced gift shop trinket		KEEPSAKE A unique piece of physical culture

2 tips for avoiding the stereotypes:

- 1 BE RESPECTFUL**
Wherever you are, be respectful of the cultural traditions and values of the place you're visiting.
- 2 BE YOURSELF**
Don't disregard or disown your own identity. Stay true to yourself, while still acclimating to the present culture.

Presented by www.landoftravel.com

Fig. 3.4 Differences between Tourist and Travellers (source: www.landoftravel.com)

CASE STUDY: Reef Check Foundation

The fundamental role of non-government organizations (NGOs) in the conservation of natural resources through their support of marine ecotourism as a tool for positive change in coastal settings is exemplified by the Reef Check initiative "Get Involved, Go MAD (Make a Difference)".

Reef Check Foundation (www.reefcheck.org) is an international non-profit organization that aims to protect coral reefs worldwide and rocky reefs in California, USA through education, research and conservation. In its core work, Reef Check trains citizen scientists globally to perform standardized scientifically robust surveys of tropical coral reefs and California's rocky reefs and kelp forests, and makes this survey data freely available online (<http://data.reefcheck.org>). Reef Check aims to achieve two complimentary goals through its citizen science programs. First, detailed data about the state and trends of the health of reef ecosystems is used to make informed management decisions at the local level, and can inform policy at a regional and global level. Second, engaging community members as citizen scientists in the collection of data and the understanding of reef health leads to greater awareness about ocean health issues, which in turn may lead to specific marine conservation actions and projects.

Reef Check Malaysia with the slogan "Get Involved, Go MAD (Make a Difference)" suggest many ways to play a role in helping protect and save the coral reefs in Malaysia and the marine environment in general:

What can we do at home?

(source: <https://www.reefcheck.org.my/get-involved>)

- Reduce, reuse and recycle
- Turn off your electrical appliances at the wall. Leaving them on standby with the little red light on still uses up electricity
- Turn off lights and fans when not in use
- When buying products, look out for their efficiency grade and rating
- Use public transport more often. If you really have to drive, try carpooling
- Avoid using household cleaning products containing harmful chemicals. This will get washed down the drain and eventually end up in the sea. You can buy eco-friendly products or better yet, make your own out of natural substances like vinegar and lemon juice
- Buy locally produced food and drinks. This reduces the carbon footprint of your diet
- Eat organic food. They are grown without insecticides and pesticides
- Turn off the tap while brushing your teeth. You can save 5-10 liters of water a day
- It rains almost half the year in Malaysia. Collect it to water your garden

-
- Start a compost bin at home to reduce the amount of trash you throw out every day. The compost will become fertile soil which you can then use
 - Recycle your paper. Papers with a clean side can be reused or made into a notepad. If you have to buy paper, buy recycled paper
 - Give away your unwanted clothes to charity. There's someone out there who will want that t-shirt that you think is too un-cool for you
 - Bring your own reusable bags when you go shopping
 - Most importantly, don't be shy to be an advocate of green living!

What can we do when we are travelling?

(source: <https://www.reefcheck.org.my/get-involved>)

- Buy products that are locally produced and sourced
 - DO NOT buy souvenirs made out of corals or sea shells
 - Take time to educate yourself about the local customs
 - Choose a hotel or resort that makes the effort to reduce their impact on the environment
 - Minimize your electricity consumption, e.g. turn off your air conditioning when not in the room
 - Minimize your water usage
 - Help to reduce plastic waste by re-using drinking water bottles
 - Use biodegradable products whenever possible
 - Minimize waste by recycling
-

-
- If hiring the services of a guide, try to ensure that they have professional certification

What can we do when visiting the islands or reefs?

(source: <https://www.reefcheck.org.my/get-involved>)

- Do not collect any seashells or dead corals on the beach; they provide shelter to small animals and produce sand over a long period of time
- Do not touch corals. They are fragile animals that die and break easily under pressure
- Do not wear fins in shallow areas or stand on corals with them. It takes many years for corals to grow back once they are broken
- Dispose your trash in the nearest bin. Do not litter into the sea. It can kill marine life
- Do not feed the marine animals as it will disrupt their feeding habits and behavior
- Look for Green Fins certified dive centers if you wish to snorkel or dive

CASE STUDY: Green Fins

The Green Fins (www.greenfins.net) initiative aims to protect and conserve coral reefs through environmentally friendly guidelines that promote a sustainable diving and snorkeling industry. The Green Fins initiative has developed a comprehensive set of guidelines to encourage best practices for an environmentally friendly scuba diving industry known as the Green Fins Code of Conduct. Green Fins' Code of Conduct was developed in 2004 through a collaborative effort between members of the diving industry, the Thailand government, UNEP and the Coral Reef Alliance (Hunt et al. 2013). Green Fins is coordinated internationally by The Reef-World Foundation in partnership with the UN Environment.

Green Fins is a conservation management approach that has been adopted by 11 countries and nearly 600 individual marine tourism companies since its inception in 2004. Green Fins encourages and empowers members of the diving industry to act to reduce the pressures on coral reefs by offering dive and snorkel companies practical, low-cost alternatives to harmful practices as well as providing strategic support and resources.

The Green Fins training and evaluation system encourages the implementation of best practices. Once a dive center signs to become a member of Green Fins, it receives internal environmental training and undergoes an initial environmental assessment. Training on best practices for environmentally friendly diving, local and global environmental and conservation issues, and marine ecology is taught by a Green Fins coordinator directly to the dive staff. The basic training and teaching materials have been translated into commonly used languages (Hunt et al. 2013).

Members receive annual assessments, training and feedback to help them reduce their environmental impact in line with the Code of Conduct (Fig. 3.5 – Fig. 3.8). By reducing the local direct and indirect pressures tourism puts on coral reefs, it helps make corals healthier and more resilient to other stressors such as the effects of climate change.

Code of Conduct

As a Green Fins Member, you are expected to:

- 1 Adopt the Green Fins mission statement
- 2 Display the adopted Green Fins agreement for the public to see
- 3 Adhere to the 'Green Fins' Friendly Diving and Snorkelling Guidelines and act as a responsible role model for guests
- 4 Participate in regular underwater cleanups at dive operator selected sites
- 5 Participate in the development and implementation of a mooring buoy program and actively use moorings, drift or hand place anchors for boats
- 6 Prohibit the sales of corals and other marine life at the dive operation
- 7 Participate in regular coral reef monitoring and report coral reef monitoring data to a regional coral reef database
- 8 Provide adequate garbage facilities on board facility's vessel and deal with responsibly
- 9 Operate under a 'minimum discharge' policy
- 10 Abide by all local, regional, national and international environmental laws, regulations and customs
- 11 Provide guests with an explanation of Green Fins' Friendly Diving and Snorkelling Guidelines in pre dive briefings
- 12 Provide training, briefing or literature for employees and guests regarding good environmental practices for snorkeling, diving, boating, marine wildlife interaction and other marine recreational activities
- 13 Provide staff and guests with public awareness and environmental materials (ID books, pamphlets etc)
- 14 Provide guests with information on local Marine Protected Areas, environmental rules and regulations
- 15 Promote a strict 'No Touch' policy for all reef diving and snorkelling.

Fig. 3.5 Green Fins code of conduct (source: Green Fins, www.greenfins.net)

Guidelines to the Code of Conduct

As a Green Fins member this dive centre is committed to protecting the marine environment by following this best practice.
If you notice lack of compliance to any of the following practices please report to info@greenfins.net.

GREEN FINS: Best Practices for the Dive Operation		GREEN FINS: Best Practices for the Dive Staff	
1	Display Green Fins certificate and posters in centre and on boat	1	Be excellent role models and follow <i>The Environmentally Friendly Diving and Snorkeling Guidelines</i>
2	Identify and train someone as your "Green Fins Champion"	2	Always provide briefings and enforce a strict "no touch" environmental policy
3	Educate all dive staff on <i>The Environmentally Friendly Diving and Snorkeling Guidelines</i> annually	3	Always use mooring buoys and install and maintain where possible
4	Adopt "minimum discharge" and "responsible garbage" policies through safe collection and disposal of hazardous waste. E.g. use eco-friendly cleaning products, recycle, no littering and no fish feeding	4	Know and tell guests about environmental rules and where relevant, marine protected areas
5	No spear fishing or sale and display of corals / marine life	5	Participate in regular beach and underwater cleanups
6	Promote good buoyancy, species ID, and marine monitoring courses (e.g. Reef Watch) and teach careful finning and photography skills	6	Participate in reef and marine life monitoring and offer ID books and posters of marine life
7	Ensure inexperienced swimmers wear life jackets when snorkeling	7	Prohibit the collection, sale and display of marine life and do not support the shark fin trade

Fig. 3.6 Guidelines for the Green Fins code of conduct (source: Green Fins, www.greenfins.net)

Guidelines to the Code of Conduct

As a **Green Fins** member this dive centre is committed to protecting the marine environment by following this best practice.
If you notice lack of compliance to any of the following practices please report to info@greenfins.net.

GREEN FINS: Best Practice for Customers

As a Green Fins member we are committed to protecting our marine life, we ask our customers to please help us by following these simple guidelines.

**7 THINGS
DIVERS
MUST DO**

✓

- Respect marine life & shoot photos without disturbing the environment
- Support conservation & champion Green Fins
- Practice buoyancy control & photography skills
- Ensure all equipment is secured & do not drag over reefs
- Practice advanced finning techniques
- Only touch rock or dead coral if necessary
- Avoid stirring up sediment by keeping your distance

**7 THINGS
DIVERS
MUST NOT DO**

X

- Do not litter
- Do not wear gloves
- Do not feed the fish
- Do not chase, touch, poke, spear or capture marine life
- Do not collect marine life souvenirs – it may be **ILLEGAL**
- Do not place cameras on reefs or move marine life to capture a better shot
- Do not touch or step on coral

Fig. 3.7 Green Fins divers best practices (source: Green Fins, www.greenfins.net)

- No stepping on coral
- No stirring the sediment
- No touching or chasing marine life
- No gloves
- No feeding fish
- No littering
- No spearfishing
- Do not support shark finning
- Don't buy souvenirs of coral and marine life
- Do not collect dead or alive marine life
- Do not anchor on coral reefs
- Use mooring buoys
- Wear a life jacket when snorkelling
- Report environmental violations
- Join in conservation projects

Fig. 3.8 Environmental briefing card (source: Green Fins, www.greenfins.net)

Green Fins also provide useful infographic, easily to understand, on environmental issues (Fig. 3.9). This approach should increase the awareness about environmental conservation among tourists and guests who are in Green Fins facilities.

Fig. 3.9 Several examples of Green Fins infographic about different environmental issues (source: Green Fins, www.greenfins.net)

CASE STUDY: Project Aware

Project AWARE (www.projectaware.org) is a non-profit organisation working with volunteer scuba divers. With offices in the UK, US, and Australia, Project AWARE supports divers acting in their communities to protect the ocean. It offers educational tools and resources that inspire action for ocean protection. For examples, they provide posters such as "I am an Eco-Tourist" and the "10 tips for divers to protect the ocean planet" and poster to increase a sense of belonging in a community who aims to protect the environment (Fig. 3.10 and Fig. 3.11).

Fig. 3.10 Example of a poster that represents a way of thinking and living (source: Project AWARE, www.projectaware.org)

10 Tips for Divers to Protect the Ocean Planet

Divers share a deep connection with the ocean. You can make a difference for ocean protection every time you dive, travel and more.

Be a Buoyancy Expert

Underwater plants and animals are more fragile than they appear. The swipe of a fin, bump of your camera or even a touch can destroy decades of coral growth, damage a plant or harm an animal. Streamline your scuba and photo gear, keep your dive skills sharp, perfect your underwater photo techniques and continue your dive training to fine-tune your skills. Always be aware of your body, dive gear and photo equipment to avoid contact with the natural environment.

Be a Role Model

New scuba divers are being trained and certified every day. Regardless of your experience level, be sure to set a good example for others when interacting with the environment—while underwater and on land.

Take Only Photos - Leave Only Bubbles

Nearly everything natural found underwater is alive or will be used by a living creature. If you take a coral, shell or animal, you can disturb the delicate balance and add to the depletion of dive sites for future generations.

Protect Underwater Life

Choose not to touch, feed, handle, chase or ride anything underwater. Your actions may stress the animal, interrupt feeding and mating behavior or provoke aggressive behavior. Understand and respect underwater life and follow all local laws and regulations.

Become a Debris Activist

An astonishing amount of waste makes its way underwater, reaching even the most remote ocean areas. Once there, it kills wildlife, destroys habitats and threatens our health and economy. Don't let your dives go to waste. Remove and report what doesn't belong underwater every time you dive. Make a conscious effort to buy green, buy local and, when possible, buy less.

Make Responsible Seafood Choices

Overfishing leads to species declines while harmful fishing practices damage and pollute underwater ecosystems. You play a critical role as a consumer. If seafood is part of your meal selection, ensure you're choosing sustainably sourced species and encourage others, including restaurants and shop owners, to do the same.

Take Action

Scuba divers are some of the strongest ocean advocates on the planet. Now, more than ever, divers like you are taking a stand. Speak out for conservation, share your underwater images, report environmental damage to authorities and campaign for change.

Be an Eco-tourist

Make informed decisions when choosing and visiting a destination. Choose facilities dedicated to responsible social and environmental business practices that include water conservation, energy reduction, proper waste disposal, use of mooring buoys and respect for local cultures, laws and regulations.

Shrink Your Carbon Footprint

Global warming and ocean acidification are putting your favorite animals and the whole ocean planet at risk. Do your part by understanding and reducing your carbon footprint and look for ways to offset what you can't reduce.

Give Back

Ocean protection depends on all of our actions, large and small. Investing in the ocean protects our planet and lets the dive adventure live on. Donate or fundraise for ocean protection to fuel the grassroots action and policy change necessary to ensure a clean, healthy ocean planet.

Thank you for giving the ocean planet the protections it deserves!
Take action with us at
PROJECTAWARE.ORG

Fig. 3.11 Good practices for divers (source: Project AWARE, www.projectaware.org)

CASE STUDY: Sailing World Cup Series

Traveling by sail is a way to move in a sustainable and responsible way to rediscover the rhythms of nature. Sailing means moving silently pushed by the wind with the use of fuel reduced to a minimum, is managing better the reserves of water and electricity without deprivation, but only by reshaping the daily attitudes, and not to use disposable plastic to prevent error flying overboard and not to fill the spaces for waste (Fig. 3.12).

The World Cup Series regatta in America banned the use of plastic and promoted series of sustainable practices for participating boats (Fig. 3.13).

This event is a
single-use plastic
FREE ZONE

USA 2019
World Cup
Series

Our Sustainability Team Needs You

5 simple steps...

1 Bring
a Bottle

Bring your own **personal reusable water bottle(s)** to use at our water fountains. If you use powdered sports drink sachets, please bring them to use in your reusable water bottle.

2 Say No to
Single-use

No plastic bags or other single-use plastic items (such as cutlery, bottles or bags) are allowed at the venue or hotel. Please bring only **reusable items** such as canvas bags and food containers.

3 Don't be
Trashy

Please **recycle**. All waste must be disposed of in proper waste receptacles for recycling, composting, and landfill, which will be located around the venue with clear signage.

4 H2O
Rules

Please clean your boat using **water only**. Deck soaps contain phosphates and nitrates that can dramatically affect water quality and can harm sea life. And, don't leave the water running!

5 Sun Safe,
Reef Safe

Please use only **reef safe sunscreens**. Sunscreens with oxybenzone contaminate the water and are harmful to marine life.

Help us protect and restore
the waters of the world

Fig. 3.12 Best practices for sailors (source: World Cup Series, www.sailing.org/worldcup)

This event is a single-use plastic FREE ZONE

USA 2019 World Cup Series

9 simple Sustainability steps for support boats

1 Stop the Drops!

When fueling, please fill fuel tanks slowly and use provided absorbent pads to catch drips and spills. **Don't overflow your fuel tank.** Try to leave the tank 10% empty to allow fuel to expand as it warms.

2 Prevent Leaks

Please **make sure your engine is well maintained** to make sure there are no oil or fuel leaks.

3 Slow Down

Try to reduce fuel consumption by turning off your boat (when safe to do so), anchoring instead of idling and reducing your speeds to a steady pace.

4 Leave a clean wake

Prevent marine debris. **Keep your trash secure on board** so it does not blow into the water.

5 Don't be Trashy

Keep **recycling** and waste separated on your boat to easily dispose of properly when on land.

6 Secure your mess

Please help **keep the boat park tidy.** Electrical tape and packaging can all blow into the water.

7 Help your Sailor

Help your sailor by carrying large volume containers of water to refill sailors' drinks bottle – avoiding single-use plastic bottles.

8 Do not Disturb

At the helm, please take care **not to disturb wildlife** and keep an eye out for slow moving manatees. Keep to marked channels and speed limits which are in place in areas where manatees swim.

9 Wash the RIB

Please **wash down your boat** with fresh water before transporting your boat to another location. This stops the spread of invasive species.

Help us protect and restore the waters of the world
Thank you

Fig. 3.13 Sustainability steps for support boats (source: World Cup Series, www.sailing.org/worldcup)

CASE STUDY: Clean Sea Life

Clean Sea Life (LIFE15 GIE / IT / 000999; www.cleanselife.it), is a LIFE project co-funded by the European Union.

The project aims to increase public attention on the amount of waste present at sea and on beaches, show how we are responsible for it and promote active and constant commitment to the environment. In addition to awareness-raising activities, the project is identifying best practices for the prevention and management of marine litter

The three principles of Clean Sea Life are:

1. do not throw anything
2. collect
3. reduce – reuse – recycle

The following are informative posters of the Clean Sea Life project for schools, recreational boaters, divers and fishermen. The posters contain information on the marine environment and threats, and suggestions and good behavioural practices to avoid polluting the marine environment (Fig. 3.14).

TUTTI INSIEME PER UN MARE PULITO

CLEAN SEA *Life* LIFE15 GIE/IT/000999

FAI LA TUA PROMESSA AL MARE!

- ★ Non perdere rifiuti nell'ambiente
- ★ Quando puoi raccogli qualcosa dalla spiaggia o dal mare
- ★ Utilizza meno plastica usa&getta, e ricicla meglio e di più

Per un mare pulito, libero dai rifiuti!

ORGANIZAZIONE: PARTNERI ESTERI:

Realizzato con il contributo dello strumento Finanziario LIFE dell'Unione Europea

TUTTI INSIEME PER UN MARE PULITO

CLEAN SEA *Life* LIFE15 GIE/IT/000999

Dipartisti, educiamo a rispettare il mare

I rifiuti marini, soprattutto quelli in plastica, possono vagare ovunque, trasportati dalle onde e dal vento, fino a raggiungere i luoghi più inespugnati. Sulle nostre spiagge, infatti, si trovano mediamente 670 rifiuti ogni 100 metri². In particolare i mozziconi di sigaretta sono uno dei rifiuti maggiormente presenti sulle spiagge di tutto il mondo, con un danno ambientale aggravato dalle oltre 130 sostanze chimiche contenute nel filtro¹. Clean Sea Life coinvolge gli amanti del mare in una straordinaria campagna di pulizia di coste e fondali d'Italia. Migliaia di dipartisti, pescatori, subacquei e amanti del mare hanno aderito e stanno cambiando il volto del mare.

Ogni giorno mentre navighi, impegnati a:

- NON GETTARE** in mare alcun rifiuto (inclusi i mozziconi di sigaretta)
- RACCOLGERE**, quando possibile, i rifiuti galleggianti
- LIMITARE** l'uso della plastica usa&getta, **RICICLARE** e fare la **DIFFERENZIATA**.

¹ Dati aggiornati: Marine Waste Life 2017
² Data: ISO (International Organization of Standards and Technology) Technical Note, What's in a Cigarette January 2017

PRENDIAMOCI CURA DELLA BIODIVERSITÀ: teniamo il mare pulito, libero dai rifiuti!

Per impegnarti nella difesa del mare vai su: www.cleansealife.it

ORGANIZAZIONE: PARTNERI ESTERI:

Realizzato con il contributo dello strumento Finanziario LIFE dell'Unione Europea

TUTTI INSIEME PER UN MARE PULITO

CLEAN SEA *Life* LIFE15 GIE/IT/000999

Subacquei, occorre il vostro aiuto!

Nel Mediterraneo sono oltre 180 le specie che possono incorrere nell'ingestione accidentale di rifiuti, soprattutto quelli in plastica: tartarughe, mammiferi e uccelli marini possono morire per soffocamento oppure restare intrappolati in lenze, cime, ami, esche, nasse e altri tipi di attrezzature. Clean Sea Life coinvolge gli amanti del mare in una straordinaria campagna di pulizia di coste e fondali d'Italia. Migliaia di subacquei, dipartisti, pescatori e amanti del mare hanno già aderito e stanno cambiando il volto del mare.

Immersione dopo immersione, impegnati a:

- NON GETTARE** nulla in mare (neanche la sigaretta!)
- RACCOLGERE** i piccoli oggetti che trovi sui fondali
- USARE MENO** plastica usa&getta, **RICICLARE** meglio e di più!

Se sei un istruttore o lavori in un diving, **ORGANIZZA UNA PULIZIA** dei fondali ogni anno e mantieni puliti i tuoi punti di immersione.

PRENDIAMOCI CURA DELLA BIODIVERSITÀ: teniamo il mare pulito, libero dai rifiuti!

Per impegnarti nella difesa del mare vai su: www.cleansealife.it

ORGANIZAZIONE: PARTNERI ESTERI:

Realizzato con il contributo dello strumento Finanziario LIFE dell'Unione Europea

TUTTI INSIEME PER UN MARE PULITO

CLEAN SEA *Life* LIFE15 GIE/IT/000999

Pescatori non siate "distratti"

Le reti e gli attrezzi da pesca abbandonati o persi in mare possono provocare danni alla fauna marina: tartarughe, mammiferi e uccelli marini possono morire per soffocamento dovuto all'ingestione accidentale di rifiuti scambiati per cibo oppure possono restare intrappolati nelle reti e negli attrezzi di cattura professionale. Clean Sea Life coinvolge gli amanti del mare in una straordinaria campagna di pulizia di coste e fondali d'Italia. Migliaia di pescatori, subacquei, dipartisti e amanti del mare hanno aderito e stanno cambiando il volto del mare.

Ogni volta che vivi il mare, impegnati a:

- NON LASCIARE** alcun tipo di rifiuto in spiaggia o in mare
- RACCOLGERE** gli oggetti abbandonati, anche se non da te
- LIMITARE** l'uso della plastica usa&getta, **RICICLARE** e fare la **DIFFERENZIATA**.

PRENDIAMOCI CURA DELLA BIODIVERSITÀ: teniamo il mare pulito, libero dai rifiuti!

Per impegnarti nella difesa del mare vai su: www.cleansealife.it

ORGANIZAZIONE: PARTNERI ESTERI:

Realizzato con il contributo dello strumento Finanziario LIFE dell'Unione Europea

Fig. 3.14 Informative poster for: top left, recreational children and schools; top right, recreational boaters; bottom left, scuba divers and snorkelers; and bottom right, recreational fishers (source: Clean Sea Life, www.cleansealife.it)

3.3 Conservation, participation and awareness

Outlining a profile for ecotourists is not easy, but several studies have identified characteristics common to ecotourists and their preferences. According to (Ballantine and Eagles 1994), ecotourists have the following eight characteristics:

1. Possession of environmental ethics
2. Willingness not to degrade the resource
3. Focus on intrinsic rather than extrinsic motivation
4. Biocentric orientation instead of anthropocentric
5. Aim to promote wildlife and the environment
6. Strive to have direct experience with the natural environment
7. Expect education and appreciation
8. High cognitive and affective dimensions

As well as having a preference for outdoor activities and in contact with nature, ecotourists prefer to travel in small groups and have a personalized service (Weaver 2002). They are generally frequent and expert travellers, who ask for information, often detailed, on the destinations they visit (Wight 1996, Galley and Clifton 2004, Wearing and Neil 2009). In general, luxury accommodation and nightlife are less important for ecotourists than learning about local cultures and savouring habits and food (Wight 1996, Galley and Clifton 2004, Wearing and Neil 2009). By understanding the motivations of ecotourists, the local community will be in a better position to meet these needs and expectations (e.g. Lucrezi et al. 2017, Lucrezi and Saayman 2017).

According to Pearce 1984, "the tourist's own experience and knowledge; and the features of the setting at hand would appear to be a major requirement for promoting the tourist's memory and the recall of the setting". The behaviour of the tourist is influenced not only by the information that the environmental guides provide, but also if the tourist can remember this information. When you love something, you know it, and by knowing it, you learn to protect it. The person, or the tourist, who learns to know better a natural environment, or certain aspects of it, increases his awareness of the environment in general and of the possible disturbances that can impact it. Greater awareness of environmental problems also implies better conservation because of learning and employing habitual behaviours aimed at protecting natural heritage.

The role that a guide has is complex. The guide is an educator who with his knowledge, and behaviour, becomes a role model for the tourist and the community. The information it provides should guide tourists to a greater sensitivity towards the environment and undertake active behaviour to safeguard the natural heritage.

The ecotourist is more inclined to make the information provided by the guide on the environment his own and memorize it since the ecotourist has travelled with a specific interest on the issue of environmental impact and interaction. However, involving all tourists more with brief summaries on the environmental characteristics of the place they are visiting would make them more respectful towards the environment.

A potential cause of the difference in tourist behaviour is the perception that the individual is aware of what "minimal impacts" actually are. Often people do not make changes in their behaviour and habits that benefit the environment until they realize that it is damaged. The ecotourist adopts an

eco-centric vision compared to an anthropocentric one: he is preventive in an attempt to mitigate the impacts from the moment he begins the journey and strives to leave the environment as he finds it (Wearing and Neil 2009). Not all tourists share this vision and behaviour, in fact mainstream tourist often tend to want to adapt the environment to suit their needs and usual behaviours, rather than adapting their behaviour according to the environment in which they are guests.

CASE STUDY: Seagrasses anchorage

Seagrasses worldwide are noted for suffering from mechanical damage caused by boat anchoring (Francour et al. 1999) or moorings (Walker et al. 1989, Hastings et al. 1995). Mainly, this happens in coastal areas subjected to intense recreational activity and / or in sites highly frequented by boaters (e.g. marine protected areas or coastal urbanised areas; Francour et al. 1999). Different strategies have been put into practice to reduce such impacts on seagrasses (i.e. by anchoring bans or by deploying boat moorings), especially within marine protected areas (MPAs) or in coastal urbanised areas. For example, boat number and size have been limited, anchoring has been restricted in certain periods of the year and moorings of various shape and type have been deployed (Milazzo et al. 2002). More recently, in consideration that few marine protected area management bodies or local administrations have the resources to enforce their anchorage regulations, the self-regulatory approach based on informing and educating boaters has been preferred in several cases (Milazzo et al. 2004).

Milazzo et al. 2004 experimentally quantify the damage caused to *Posidonia oceanica* shoot density by anchoring at Ustica Island MPA. Three different anchor types (Hall, Danforth and Folding grapnel) had shown differed in the levels of damage inflicted on the *P. oceanica* meadows at Ustica Island MPA. In particular, the use of the Hall type anchor seems to be preferable to minimise this impact in comparison with the other two anchor types.

The type of anchor must be chosen based on the prevailing type of seabed to ensure a safe docking. However, with the same anchors and bottom typology, knowing and educating which of these is least harmful to marine organisms could reduce impacts.

In general, in sites mainly frequented by small boats using light anchors, it could be important to implement a self-regulatory approach based on educating and informing boaters on correct anchor types to use when anchoring on *P. oceanica* (Milazzo et al. 2004).

CASE STUDY: Educational video-briefing

Scuba diving is generally considered a low impact activity with high educational potential. Recreational divers are increasingly involved in marine conservation through their activism, citizen science, monetary donations and participation in conservation initiatives (Hammerton et al. 2012, Holt et al. 2013).

However, ecological damages caused by divers, such as the Red Sea (Zakai and Chadwick-Furman 2002, Hasler and Ott 2008) and Florida, United States (Krieger and Chadwick 2013), have occurred in tropical regions intensively frequented by tourists.

Several studies have assessed the negative impacts of underwater tourism and provided approaches to mitigate the harmful effects on coral reefs, such as the use of pre-dive educational briefings and close underwater supervision by dive leaders (Renfro and Chadwick 2017).

A study of Giglio et al. 2018 in Arraial do Cabo Marine Extractive Reserve (ACMER), Brazil, tested the use of educational video briefing to change the divers' behaviour.

The educational video-briefing has been shown to recreational divers before diving (www.youtube.com/watch?v=GrGT7fvnqaw). The video provided environmental information to divers and enhanced their use of low-impact diving techniques. In particular, It contains five major messages to divers concerning proper reef etiquette: (1) do not collect anything; (2) do not touch the animals; (3) make your descent over a sandy bottom; (4) establish neutral buoyancy and maintain a horizontal swimming posture; and (5) photographers especially should focus on not touching the reef.

The study reveals that divers who received the video-briefing exhibited low-impact behaviours: low rates of contact with and damage to benthic reef

organisms. It, therefore, highlight the efficacy of video-briefings as an educational tool to inform divers about environmentally responsible practices and mitigate the negative impacts of tourism in natural ecosystems (Giglio et al. 2018).

CASE STUDY: Snorkelling underwater self-guided routes

The use of natural coastal areas for underwater marine activities such as snorkelling is growing. Snorkelling is particularly important marine-based tourism activity, allowing people to visit underwater cultural and natural structures and permitting direct human interaction with the environment (Garrod and Gössling 2008). It ensures wide appeal and great participation, while it requires less equipment and training than diving, and it is an excellent tool for education.

Underwater snorkelling routes have been used since 1958 as a tool for concentrating snorkelers in less sensitive areas, to provide environmental information, and to increase environmental awareness by encouraging appropriate behaviours and understanding of marine environment (e.g. Plathong et al. 2000, Claudet et al. 2010, Rangel et al. 2015).

In Rangel et al. 2015 study, three underwater self-guided routes were designed at Marinha Beach (Algarve, Portugal), as a way to enhance biodiversity awareness and reduce potential impacts on marine features, such as protect important seagrass meadows of *Cymodocea nodosa*.

At Marinha Beach in the Cerbère-Banyuls Natural Marine Reserve, the information regarding the self-guided snorkelling routes was firstly provided through pre-dive briefings. Once inside the water, acrylic slates attached to buoys provided detailed information on the surrounding environment (Rangel et al. 2015).

Snorkelers' opinions and perceptions about several issues related to the routes' environmental education role were investigated by questionnaires after the snorkelling activity. Results indicate that the vast majority of snorkelers were of the opinion that routes were good for biodiversity and

would return to repeat the dive and that they have learned new information on local biodiversity.

If properly addressed, in situ education can help to control snorkelers impacts' and can raise environmental awareness, resulting in a satisfactory way of engaging snorkelers in the protection and in the conservation of the visited environments, thereby preventing negative ecological impacts (Rangel et al. 2015).

In addition, Townsend 2008 stresses that the challenge is to provide this information in order to increase visitors' satisfaction and interest in these problems. The interpretation of a site through panels and flyers increases the appreciation of visitors for the surrounding areas and encourages empathy with the site (Townsend 2008).

Guided tours are a useful tool to increase the awareness, and involvement of tourists and also a means of controlling where visitors go and what they do. A trained guide accompanying a group discusses the environmental characteristics along a predetermined route, adding further details, perspectives or curiosity based on the group's interests and responses (Wearing and Neil 2009). In the case of marine tourism, in addition to the briefing for diving and snorkelling already treated, guided tours can also be interpreted as tour boats or kayak trips. One of the strengths of the guided tours is that the guide can adapt to what is said to the particular interest of each group, such as the geology of the coast or biology of the marine habitats. Guides who work for ecotourism operators must be knowledgeable about many environmental aspects of the tour and preferably be fluent in different languages. One of the limitations of guided tours is their high cost per visitor and their continuous dependence on the personality and commitment of the guide to offer a high-quality experience. However, some of the visitors may find guides that interfere with their desired sense of freedom.

CASE STUDY: Sea Kayaking Sustainability Practices

Since 1996, The Sunny Cove, a local company in Alaska, has been taking guided kayak tours and wildlife cruises.

All of their guides are trained well above industry standards. They are all Wilderness First Responders and are assessed for Level 3 certifications from the American Canoe Association. Their commitment to the environment and passion for wildlife and natural beauty is reflected in their quality of service to the guests.

Sunny Cove was recently awarded a gold-level certification by Adventure Green Alaska (AGA, www.adventuregreenalaska.org). AGA is a certification program for tourism businesses operating in Alaska that meet specific standards of economic, environmental and social sustainability.

Sunny Cove has adopted the “Sea Kayaking Sustainability Practices”, which learning is among the training program for the staff.

Sunny Cove Sea Kayaking Sustainability Practices

(<https://www.sunnycove.com/sustainable-kayaking>)

1. We limit our footprint to select areas within Resurrection Bay and Kenai Fjords National Park. We do not need to go to the most remote or least visited areas of the park to provide our clients with an authentic wilderness experience. We have chosen areas that are best able to absorb our passing and provide a few amenities (such as bear-proof food storage boxes), which help keep the wildlife wild
2. Sunny Cove practices Leave No Trace ethics. This practice is not limited to camping. We have not applied for permits to store

equipment in the field or to build semi-permanent camps on public lands. We practice what we preach

3. We serve as advocates to preserve and protect the natural environment that sustains us. Sunny Cove has taken an active role in advocating for wildlands to be left wild and in supporting conservation efforts and issues. This includes supporting local conservation organizations with donations and volunteer work
4. We provide our guide staff with the best natural history training possible. Each spring we bring in an expert to work with our staff. Our staff training is usually more than three weeks in length, some of which is focused on natural history information. For many years we have incorporated climate change information into our training sessions and have made that information available to our clients. Sunny Cove has been one of the organizers of a guide training day, which brings together all the commercial kayaking companies and local land management agencies. We are also members of a local paddling group helping to educate fellow kayakers and residents of Seward on various issues involving the environment and sustainability
5. We are visitors to our marine habitat and our presence can adversely impact the residents. To ensure we limit our impact, Sunny Cove follows Marine Mammal viewing guidelines and educates our guests about the potentially negative impact we humans can have on plants and animals. It is our goal to observe wildlife without altering their normal behaviour patterns and to experience Resurrection Bay and Kenai Fjords National Park without leaving a trace

-
6. We are supportive of our local community. We buy most of our supplies from local businesses and nearly all of our supplies from Alaskan businesses. We also support our local charities and volunteer organizations. We currently provide support to over 20 Alaska non-profit organizations. Several of our staff members are board members for local non-profits and they donate hundreds of volunteer hours toward their respective causes
 7. We buy (and on a personal level harvest) local foods like salmon, halibut and berries. We want our clients to experience the best of our local cuisine. Very little of our trip food is wasted. Our guide staff does a good job consuming any leftovers
 8. We run our operations in the most fuel-efficient way we can. Last year we did an energy audit of our main building. This led to a construction project, which raised our energy rating nearly 2 stars. We provide bicycles for our staff, offer car-pooling for work transport and use our vehicles as little as possible

CASE STUDY: SOS flyer - Sustainability and safety at sea

A useful product to point out the collaboration among different partners is the SOS flyer: sustainability and safety at sea (Fig. 3.15). It was developed as part of a program agreement between the Port Authority Command and the Ministry of the Environment aimed at promoting the #PlasticfreeGC environmental communication and education campaign. Furthermore, the flyer, created in collaboration with the InforMare association, provides simple rules to follow for the safety and sustainability of living by the sea and also offers ideas for participating in citizen science projects.

GUARDIA COSTIERA

SOS: sostenibilità e sicurezza in mare

Semplici regole per una subacquea sicura e sostenibile

Sostenibilità	Sicurezza
<p>Mantieni sempre un buon assetto anche quando fai foto o video, per ridurre i consumi e tutelare l'ambiente marino</p>	<p>Per l'emergenza in mare è attivo il numero blu 1530 gratuito su tutto il territorio nazionale e attivo tutti i giorni 24 ore su 24</p>
<p>Se hai una barca fai attenzione a non gettare l'ancora sulla Posidonia oceanica: è una pianta marina protetta</p>	<p>Porta con te una boa segnasub e ricorda di rimanere entro un raggio di 50 mt</p>
<p>Fai attenzione a non buttare nessun tipo di rifiuto né in mare né in terra</p>	<p>Ricordati di fare ogni anno una visita medico sportiva che certifichi il tuo stato di idoneità fisica</p>
<p>Proteggi l'habitat marino. Non disperdere la plastica nell'ambiente</p>	<p>Mantieni una buona idratazione, non bere alcol e riposati nelle ore prima dell'immersione</p>
<p>Là dove possibile raccogli i rifiuti</p>	<p>Evita sforzi e salite in quota dopo l'immersione</p>
<p>Smaltisci in modo corretto olio, batterie e pile</p>	<p>Non lasciare che la tua disabilità ti impedisca di vivere il mare. Rivolgiti agli esperti.</p>
<p>Se incontri cetacei in mare non disturbarli e segnala l'avvistamento su www.cetaceifaialtensione.it</p>	<p>Ascolta con attenzione il briefing della guida prima dell'immersione e chiedi se qualcosa non è chiaro</p>
<p>Partecipa a progetti di raccolta dati. Il tuo contributo può fare davvero la differenza*</p>	<p>Non fare immersioni, né apnea o snorkeling da solo ma sempre con un compagno</p>
<p>Non toccare e non prelevare gli animali</p>	<p>Effettua la tua immersione nel limite del tuo brevetto</p>
<p>Informati sulle specie, soprattutto quelle protette, presenti nella zona di immersione</p>	<p>Fai attenzione all'efficienza delle attrezzature subacquee tue e di quelle del tuo compagno di immersione e porta con te un kit di riparazione</p>
<p>Porta sempre un pedagno di segnalazione per le emergenze. Ricordati che è obbligatorio!</p>	

* www.reefcheckmed.org

ideazione e realizzazione grafica in collaborazione con InfoMARE

Fig. 3.15 SOS flyer: sustainability and safety at sea (source: InforMare)

CASE STUDY: Brijuni National park behaviour rules

The Brijuni or the Brijuni Islands are a group of fourteen small islands in the Croatian part of the northern Adriatic Sea. The two largest islands are Veli Brijuni Island and Mali Brijuni. The boundaries of the Brijuni National Park were set in 1999 and it includes 14 islands.

The Park authorities has developed and adopt a Code of Conduct (Fig. 3.16) to protect the biodiversity and preserve the archaeological, cultural and historical, as well as geological and palaeontological sites within Brijuni National Park.

Rules for the protection of flora, fauna and the environment

(www.np-brijuni.hr/it/organizza-la-visita/informazioni-pratiche/regole-di-comportamento)

- Activities that may cause changes or damage to this protected part of the island nature and any activity that is able to change the natural aspect and compromise the landscape values of the national park are prohibited
- It is forbidden to pollute the air, soil, water, sea and seabed, that is, to carry out activities that are capable of compromising their original environmental value. In particular, it is forbidden to throw or deposit any kind of waste in the environment
- The collection, excavation, grubbing up and damage to plants are prohibited in the national park area
- In the entire area of the national park it is forbidden to introduce or plant hybrid or cloned plant species (allochthonous) or to introduce and leave free in the park hybrid or cloned animal species

-
- It is forbidden to drive out, mistreat, harass, capture, injure and kill the animal species present in the park
 - It is forbidden to catch frogs and collect snails, mushrooms and medicinal herbs, as well as any other type of collection of living and non-living natural organisms
 - Any type of hunting and hunting activities, the port and the use of firearms or other means suitable for hunting (bow and arrows, traps, nets etc.) are prohibited
 - The hunting, collection and extraction of molluscs, sea cucumbers (sea cucumbers), sea urchins and any other marine organism is prohibited
 - It is forbidden to fish, catch and extract fish from the sea, except for specific permits issued by the Park Authority in areas intended for recreational fishing

Rules for the protection of cultural heritage

- Any damage to cultural heritage is prohibited, including climbing monuments
- Excavation and subtraction of archaeological finds is prohibited
- It is forbidden to damage or extract geo-paleontological finds such as fossils from the ground

General rules for visitors

- Access to the park is allowed by land through Fažana (Fažana) and by sea through mooring in the port of Veli Brijuni
- During their stay, travel and visits within the national park, visitors are required to comply with the instructions printed on the entrance ticket, information panels and other signs posted inside the national park
- Visitors are free to move only in the areas, along the marked paths and paths intended for visits
- On the island of Veli Brijuni it is possible to rent bicycles, cars and electric scooters. Driving is prohibited outside of the marked roads
- The transfer of visitors and visits inside the national park are organized by the Park Authority
- It is not allowed to bring food and drinks into the park
- Feeding and annoying animals is not allowed
- It is forbidden to camp and camp out without the permission of the Park Authority
- Bathing is allowed on the Saluga and Jupiter beaches and on natural beaches, with the exception of the more rigid protected areas and areas where bathing is prohibited
- It is forbidden to light fires
- Smoking is prohibited outside

-
- Recreational activities are allowed only in the places provided and indicated for this purpose or with the permission of the Park Authority
 - Without the permission of the Park Authority it is not allowed to make audio-visual recordings or take photographs for commercial purposes

For pets (dogs)

- In the area of the national park, dogs and other pets cannot move freely
 - In the park, dogs must be kept tied or kept in a fenced area, or they can be led on a leash but only in areas where this is allowed. The dogs can be taken for a walk in the area of the port of Veli Brijuni, from the southern breakwater to the Pave villa and from the Magnolia villa to the northern breakwater, as well as within the fenced area of Villa Lovorka
 - Exceptionally only for therapy dogs and assistance dogs is admission to facilities open to visitors
 - Dogs that, due to their disposition, their aggressive instinct or specific training, represent a danger for the safety of people, during the transfer by ship and during the visit to the park (within the confines of the areas reserved for them) they must wear a muzzle
-

- Dog bathing is allowed in the stretch of sea that goes from the southern breakwater of the port of Veli Brijuni and extends for 50 m towards the Jupiter beach

Means of transport

- It is allowed to bring your own bicycle or scooter on the island, with at least 24 hours' notice. For the transport of bicycles or scooters on the island, an additional cost will be charged

Boats

- The stay and mooring of boats is allowed only inside the port of Veli Brijuni and in the bay of San Nicolò on the island of Mali Brijuni, or using the so-called "dead body" as anchorage in front of the mooring areas
- Staying or anchoring in the national park is not allowed, except within the ports or areas reserved for mooring
- Transit is allowed without stopping between the islands of San Girolamo and Veli Brijuni. Entry into the port of Veli Brijuni from the Gulf of Fažana and entry into the mooring area in the bay of San Nicolò on the island of Mali Brijuni is allowed only from the west side between Veli Brijuni and Mali Brijuni

Park surveillance and protection authority

- The surveillance and protection of the national park is the responsibility of the park rangers
- The park ranger is entitled to ask each visitor to show his identity card or other document suitable for ascertaining his identity. The park ranger is also entitled to inspect the visitor's luggage, means of transport or boat
- The park ranger is entitled to ask each visitor to show the entrance ticket

Fig. 3.16 Brijuni National Park code of conduct infographic (source: www.np-brijuni.hr)

3.4 Monitoring and evaluation

Ecotourism groups ideally should be small to provide a higher quality experience to the customer. That helps in the ability to keep environmental stress and impact levels to a minimum, as well as allowing the tourists' intrinsic aims to be realised (e.g. experience with the natural environment, request for education; Wearing and Neil 2009 and reference therein).

The goals of an appropriate environmental management should be: biodiversity conservation, preserve aesthetic (social / amenity) value and pursuing sustainable development. Environmental monitoring is essential to pursuing these goals (Fig. 3.17).

Fig. 3.17 Comparison between the same site after 10 years. It changed from a pristine site to a degraded ones (source: Uychiaoco et al. 2010)

Environmental monitoring means gathering data and information on ecosystems or on those people who use natural resources in response to

possible threats and specific objectives, adequately spatially replicated and repeated on a regular basis and for long time (Fig. 3.18).

Fig. 3.18 Proper environmental monitoring in space and time (source: Uychiaoco et al. 2010)

Ideally, each monitoring should follow these steps (Uychiaoco et al. 2010):

1. an initial clear definition of threats and specific objectives (general or specific)
2. the choose of appropriate sites, methods and protocol
3. an initial baseline survey and / or a pilot study
4. the continued monitoring
5. appropriate results interpretation, dissemination and response actions
6. eventually, the revise of the methods without loss compatibility with previous data

The monitoring could be ecological and socio-economic. The ecological monitoring takes into consideration physical parameters (e.g. currents, temperature, water quality) and biological parameters (e.g. organism percent cover, species or genus composition and size structure of the benthic communities, numbers, species composition, size and structure of fish populations). While the socio-economic monitoring analyses socio-economic parameters such as community population, employment levels and incomes, catch and price statistics for fisheries, education level and awareness, decision making structures in communities and tourist perceptions of the value of marine protected areas and willingness to pay for management. The monitoring should contribute to ensure sustainability (Uychiaoco et al. 2010; Fig. 3.19).

Fig. 3.19 Monitoring and sustainability (source: Uychiaoco et al. 2010)

Monitoring program consists of series of monitoring protocols that together provide a manager with the information needed to manage their natural areas. Protocol is the selections of methods and how they are used to gain information at a site. Method is the description of how the information is collected.

The monitoring program consists of three levels:

1. research monitoring provides very detailed data, but it is expensive, takes more time, requires more expertise to assess a smaller area, and it is usually design to answer a specific question
2. management monitoring adds more detail, is more expensive, takes more time and covers less area, but aims to provide the best information for MPA management, required trained staff
3. community monitoring is at a lower detail level, i.e. it covers a larger area in less time, for less cost involving trained volunteers. It is very useful as an early warning system of changes, enhances education, awareness and local stewardship pf resources through participation of community members.

Carrying Capacity (CC) and Limits of Acceptable Change (LAC) are examples of visitor planning and management frameworks for sustainable decision-making used in protected area management. When implemented, they help to protect a country's natural and cultural heritage, increase public appreciation, and manage the conflict between resource and user (Wearing and Neil 2009 and reference therein).

Carrying Capacity

Carrying capacity is important for environmental protection and sustainable development. It is a management tool for the public use of recreational areas as it provides a basis for the sustainable use of resources. It refers to the maximum use of any site without causing negative effects on resources, reducing visitor satisfaction or having a negative impact on the society, economy and culture of the area or, in other words, the levels of sustainable uses for fisheries, tourism or other activities, below which the ecosystem can cope and remain resistant and / or resilient to the use, but above which detrimental changes can occur. In fact, the concept of carrying capacity is rooted in the idea that there is a limit to the number of visitors to a tourist destination and that this limit is closely linked to the characteristics of the site. Carrying capacity limits can be difficult to quantify but are essential for environmental planning for tourism and recreation.

"Tourism Carrying Capacity" is defined by the UN World Tourism Organization as "The maximum number of people that may visit a tourist destination at the same time, without causing destruction of the physical, economic, socio-cultural environment and an unacceptable decrease in the quality of visitors' satisfaction".

There are different forms of carrying capacity referred to in tourism, here there are listed the three most commonly used:

- Physical (ecological) – which relates to the maximum number of tourists that an area is actually able to support and the extent to which the natural environment is able to tolerate interference from tourists.

-
- Socio-cultural – which relates primarily to the negative socio-cultural impacts associated with tourism development on the host population and its culture.
 - Facility or economic– which relates to the visitor experience, the extent to which a tourist destination is able to accommodate tourist functions without the loss of local activities.

The carrying capacity may be analysed in three consecutive phases: the physical carrying capacity (i.e. the ratio of available space to mean visitor space), following the actual carrying capacity (i.e. weighting the physical carrying capacity with correction factors that are site-specific), and permissible carrying capacity (i.e. establishment of the acceptable limit of use in considering the management capacity of the administration of each site).

However, the carrying capacity was not as useful as expected. The main criticism of carrying capacity is that it is fundamentally imperfect. On a practical level, it is difficult to calculate the maximum number of visitors because this also depends on other factors such as the way tourists behave. Furthermore, there is a wide range of different values and perceptions of what an "unacceptable impact" is. There are no absolute measurements of resource conditions, which can be defined as "crowding" or "damage to resources" (Stankey et al. 1985). UNESCO, for example, has expressed concern that the use of carrying capacity may give the impression that a site is better protected than it actually is, stresses that although the whole site may be outside below load capacity, part of the site may still be crowded. Although tour operators may be aware that too many visitors will degrade the environment and reduce the experience of their customers in both the

recreational and tourism sectors, there are very few examples of its use by agencies to successfully limit tourism (McCool and Lime 2001).

The limitation of this approach is that the conditions necessary to establish carrying capacity are rarely achieved in the real world and that it is applicable only to limited situations where numerical capacities may be appropriate such as parking. Instead, planning frameworks such as the limit of acceptable change are best suited to addressing visitor impact issues (McCool and Lime 2001).

CASE STUDY: Carrying capacity for recreational scuba diving

The carrying capacity concept was introduced to coral reefs in the mid-1980s (Salm 1985).

Hawkins and Roberts 1997 in order to determine if coral reefs have a safe level of carrying capacity for recreational scuba diving compared damage level to reefs subject to know levels of diving intensity within Sharm-el-Sheik in Egypt, and Saba and Bonaire Islands in the Caribbean. The authors recommended that the figure of 5,000 - 6,000 dives per site per year could be used to estimate the overall capacity of a protected area to support recreational diving, depending on the number of dive sites available, but the carrying capacity can vary with:

- number of divers
- types of divers
- divers training - education and guidance
- the types of coral growth-forms (e.g. fragile / stout)
- nature of the site (slope, current, community structure)
- natural level of coral breakage
- access to a dive site (reef walking, snorkelling or from a boat)
- type of diving (drift, swim, photography...)
- whether the diving boat is using mooring or is anchoring
- types and amount of infrastructure support
- size of a dive site

The study concluded that coral reefs could cope with more educated / environmentally aware than "naive" divers and that in some cases, the

infrastructure associated with marine tourism could cause more damage than diving themselves.

Thus, setting numerical limits on the number of divers allowed on a site (or indeed in a larger dive area) is unlikely to be effective on its own, if introduced as the sole management strategy (de Vantier and Turak 2004).

Limits of acceptable change

Limits of acceptable change (LAC) was the first of the post-carrying-capacity visitor management frameworks developed to respond to the practical and conceptual failures of carrying capacity. The framework was developed by The U.S. forest service in the 1980s. LAC methodology recognises both the social and environmental dimensions of recreational impacts, and in that, it is an extension of the Recreation opportunity spectrum (ROS) concept (ROS is a framework for prescribing carrying capacities and managing recreational impacts. It is a means of identifying and determining the diversity of recreation opportunities for a natural area or a group of natural areas, and it is based on the idea that visitor services quality is best assured by providing an array of opportunities suited to the full range of expected visitors).

LAC derives from the idea that rather than there being a threshold of visitor numbers, any tourist activity is having an impact. Therefore, management should be based on constant monitoring of the site as well as the objectives established for it. LAC gave greater emphasis to the decision of when changes to a site would become unacceptable (Stankey and McCool 1984). LAC also gave a predominant role to the capability of the competent administration to respond, in that carrying capacity would be the threshold of human activity beyond which environmental impact on the resources will result (Wolters 1991).

LAC involves both resource managers and stakeholders in:

- identifying acceptable and achievable social and resource standards
- documenting gaps between desirable and existing circumstances

- identifying management actions to close these gaps
- monitoring and evaluating management effectiveness

The LAC planning system consists of nine steps.

1. Identifying concerns and issues
2. Defining and describing opportunity classes
3. Selecting indicators of resource and social conditions
4. Carrying out an inventory of resource and social conditions
5. Specifying standards for resource and social indicators
6. Identifying alternative opportunity class allocations
7. Identifying management actions for each alternative
8. Evaluating and selecting an alternative
9. Implementing actions and monitoring conditions (Stankey et al. 1985, Payne and Graham 1993)

Operatively, with LAC a management agency determines what levels of diver-, visitor- or infrastructure- caused change or damage is acceptable (e.g. decline in coral cover of 5 %). Compliance monitoring and reactive management then aim to maintain a particular tourism site within those levels (Stankey et al. 1985). The LAC approach requires a clear:

- definition of what is acceptable (e.g. damage must not exceed the natural range of coral damage or, damage shall not exceed 10% of natural damage levels)
- identification and specification of monitoring methods
- statement of decision criteria and management actions if / when the LAC criteria are exceeded

Finally, management agency must identify the source(s) of impact and stop or control the source(s) of it (de Vantier and Turak 2004).

The LAC framework offers more opportunities for public participation, which results in a consensus planning approach to the management of natural areas (e.g. Ahn et al. 2002). However, few LAC systems have been implemented with great success and this is thought to be due to the lack of political and economic support from stakeholders (Rouphael and Hanafy 2007).

However, the LAC approach can also prove difficult to implement in practice. To set the LAC, it is necessary to define the "normal" conditions of the system and how it changes over time in relation to various disturbances, both "natural" (e.g. raising the water temperature, storms etc.) and human-induced. This was attempted through the establishment and monitoring of "control" or scientific reference sites with community structures and environmental conditions similar to the dive sites of interest (de Vantier and Turak 2004).

CASE STUDY: Limits of acceptable change at Bunaken National Park

According to the report of de Vantier and Turak 2004, North Sulawesi (Indonesia) had approximately 120 known dive sites, in five main locations (i.e. Bunaken National Park islands, southern mainland section of Bunaken National Park, North Sulawesi mainland, Lembeh Strait and Gangga - Bangka - Talise islands; Fig. 3.20).

Fig. 3.20 Diving spots in North Sulawesi, Indonesia, in 2004

To investigate the strengths and weaknesses and pressures of tourist activity, mainly related to underwater tourism, at the Bunaken National Park, the authors applied different methods and strategies (de Vantier and Turak 2004):

- The quality of dive briefings was assessed using standard survey forms.
- The coral cover was assessed by applying a modified Reef Check point-intercept protocol with improved taxonomy, while the coral breakage sets through belt transects
- Finally, the Rapid Ecological Assessment of Homestay Accommodation was assessed using standard survey forms.

They identified (de Vantier and Turak 2004):

- 40 dive operators
- 1,000 accommodations places (380 in cottages on Bunaken National Park islands)
- 11,250 divers y^{-1} (potentially up to 25,000)
- 110,000 – 225,000 dive y^{-1}
- 2,000 dive site $^{-1}$ on average
- > 6,000 dive site $^{-1}$ in the most-dived sites

They identified and discriminate between the tourism-related impacts (i.e. Diver and dive-related impacts) and Non-tourism related impacts that can affect condition of the marine environment and thus marine tourism (de Vantier and Turak 2004).

The tourism related-impacts include:

- diver damage, including standing by snorkelers
- anchor damage
- boat strike damage and propeller disturbance to shallow seagrass beds
- and fast boat speeds on shallow reefs and among divers
- pollution from solid wastes
- pollution from sewage - eutrophication
- pollution from sediment mobilization during homestay construction
- increased pressure on fisheries to supply tourists

While the non-tourism related impacts include:

- non-tourism related coastal developments
- river flooding and run-off
- storm waves
- overfishing and destructive fishing - including blast and poison fishing
- poison fishing to supply the ornamental aquarium trade
- pollution from Manado
- coral predation by crown-of-thorns seastars or *Drupella* molluscs
- coral bleaching from temperature fluctuations or other stressors

Regarding the Limits of acceptable change approach, the authors listed several recommendations for the dive sites and the level of use (de Vantier and Turak 2004):

1. Great care should be taken in opening new sites to diving, with initial assessment, regular monitoring and dive use restrictions put in place:
 - Individual dive site use-limits should be based on an initial site assessment and evaluation of the particular sensitivity of the proposed site to diving-related damage (e.g. types / morphology of corals etc.)
 - Diving activity may be capped at present levels by licensing operators currently using the National Park. Licenses may include a list the sites / reefs that operators may visit
 - Surveillance and regulatory measures may be developed in relation to the deliberate exceeding of carrying capacity limits by dive operators
 - Marine Park zoning schemes are a useful way of controlling / regulating the opening of additional dive sites
 2. A standard, simple site assessment and monitoring protocol should be developed and implemented, based on Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network protocols (English et al. 1997, Wilkinson et al. 2003, Hill and Wilkinson 2004) and the field methods employed during the de Vantier and Turak 2004 study. Variables to be monitored include levels of coral damage (i.e. numbers of fragments, numbers and proportions of broken colonies)
-

-
3. For sites to be maintained in good condition, a high degree of cooperation among dive operators is required, in relation to the setting of realistic Limits of Acceptable Change (LAC):
- LAC may be measured in terms of the levels of coral damage (i.e. numbers of fragments, numbers and proportions of broken colonies) and cover of living / broken / dead coral and rubble; fish diversity and abundance (and other indicators as appropriate), and by developing detailed, specific site inventories (e.g. notable features - spectacular fan corals etc.)
 - Reactive management decision criteria need to be developed in relation to exceeding of LAC limits
 - In respect to LAC, careful vigilance / monitoring and reactive management will be required. The statistical detection and definite assignment of diver-caused change can be complex, in relation to within-site variability -natural changes
 - The use of “control” or reference sites that are closed to diving, yet have similar community structure and other attributes is useful in terms of understanding source and impact of diving-related damage. However, in North Sulawesi there are significant difficulties associated with this approach
 - This can also be expensive and a realistic monitoring and management budget needs to be allocated
 - The dive operators themselves can achieve some aspects of monitoring and management, in association with Park
-

management staff. This is particularly important, not just for diving related impacts, but also for other disturbances that may affect quality of dive sites (e.g. coral predation by crown-of-thorns sea stars)

Sites that have been badly damaged (i.e. exceeding LAC limits) should elicit reactive management measures, such as temporary site closure to allow for regeneration, and a review of carrying capacity limits (de Vantier and Turak 2004).

3.5 Citizen science as a monitoring tool

Citizen science (CS) is the most widespread term to indicate the involvement of amateur and non-professional scientist in making observations or collecting data. Most of the CS programs are oriented to nature conservations and their number have increased worldwide in the last decades (Conrad and Hilchey 2011), including those concerning the marine environment (MCS; Thiel et al. 2014). Engaging millions of people around the world and as the resources for monitoring fail to match the scale of the question at hand, CS has become more critical in conservation science by influencing and improving management (of, e.g. MPA or fisheries) and by substantially increasing the observation capacity available (Pattengill-Semmens and Semmens 2003, Cohn 2008, Conrad and Hilchey 2011, Miller-Rushing et al. 2012, Tulloch et al. 2013, Cigliano et al. 2015, Wright et al. 2016, Burgess et al. 2017, Lucrezi et al. 2018). The growth factors are primarily the rising awareness that volunteers are a free source of skills, labour-force and computational power and secondly the existence of informatics tools that can spread the information about project easily and gathering data from the participants (Silvertown 2009, Dickinson et al. 2012, Newman et al. 2012, Cerrano et al. 2017). The dual aim of CS programs should be indeed the collection of reliable data and the increase in people's awareness and knowledge, which are essential requirements for responsible behaviours towards nature conservation. The advantage of this participatory approach lies in the opportunity to expand the ability to collect information and data in space and time, in the face of limited investment (e.g., advertising, training, web platforms and mobile apps).

Although not as prevalent as its terrestrial counterpart (Cooper et al. 2014, Theobald et al. 2015, Sullivan et al. 2017, Bradter et al. 2018), the MCS

projects have spread up from tropical coral reefs (e.g., Reef Check tropical EcoDiver program and Reef Environmental Education Foundation program; Hodgson 1999, Hodgson 2001, Pattengill-Semmens and Semmens 2003) to temperate habitats (e.g., Reef Check Mediterranean Sea Underwater Coastal Environment Monitoring protocol, Cerrano et al. 2017; British and Irish Seasearch protocols and Californian Reef Check; Pikesley et al. 2016).

Underwater CS programs that directly involve dive centres and other local stakeholders have higher probability of success, especially in the long term. Citizen science projects can enhance the ability of decision-makers, stakeholders and non-government organisations to monitor, manage and protect natural resources. While citizen volunteers are increasingly involved in local issues, and more awareness in environmental threats and careful about their everyday actions toward the environment (Alaback 2012, Conrad and Hilchey 2011, Whitelaw et al. 2003, Tulloch et al. 2013).

CASE STUDY: Reef Check Med - The Underwater Monitoring Protocol

Citizen Science (CS) projects play a relevant role in environmental education and in increasing people awareness, which lie at the basis of nature conservation. CS projects should allow expanding our ability to collect information and data in space and time, in the face of limited investments. However, data collected by CS are mostly unexploited for ecosystem-based management, both because often considered unreliable and due to the lack of appropriate analysis and interpretation tools. This is particularly true for Marine CS projects (MCS).

Reef Check Italia onlus is a non-profit scientific association dedicated to the protection and recovery of Mediterranean reefs. Founded in 2008, Reef Check Italia was born from a partnership between the Reef Check Foundation, a coral reef monitoring program officially recognised by the United Nations, and the CEM (Mediterranean Coastal Environment Monitoring) project. Reef Check Med is the set of different national associations (Fig. 3.21) that apply the same monitoring protocol for the Mediterranean Sea: the Reef Check Mediterranean Sea underwater coastal environment monitoring (U-CEM) protocol.

The U-CEM protocol ensures that the volunteer divers, after a 1-day intensive training course, including verification of their abilities, make independent observations on the presence/absence and abundance of selected taxa.

Fig. 3.21 Reef Check Mediterranean Sea web page (source: www.reefcheckmed.org)

Taxa were selected by RC scientists based on a combination of criteria including, being easily observable and identifiable underwater and one or more of the following: a Non-Indigenous Species (NIS) or a species protected under European directives or international conventions; sensitive to climate change; an ecosystem engineer; threatened by human activities or commercially exploited. Taken together, these taxa represent key aspects of Mediterranean subtidal habitats, and of the changes they may be undergoing. When it is not easy to discriminate between species, genus level was chosen, as in the case of the two protected Mediterranean seahorses.

During the training, divers or snorkellers are made aware of the importance of their contribution and learn how to search and recognize target taxa. Before diving, each participant chose which and how many of the 43 taxa will be searched for, according to the expected habitat typology and to personal motivations. This freedom of choice ensures greater attention and accuracy by the volunteers, for example, because they can select taxa they are more confident with (probably reducing errors), those they like the most (making the diving experience more satisfactory), or limit themselves

to a number of taxa they feel able to handle (which reduces pressure). Underwater, the abundance and depth range of each searched taxon are recorded, along with the type of habitat where they are encountered (picked from a list). Taxa actively searched for, but not encountered, are recorded as absent. A plastic board, bearing identification drawings, is provided to help in the task (Fig. 3.22). Recorded observations, including absence, site name and geographic coordinates, date and time, underwater visibility, survey depth range (min and max), and observation effort in terms of dedicated time, are then fed to the online database through an internet form or a dedicated app for Android smartphones (Reef Check Med App, available on the Google Play Store). Each trained participant is identified by a unique personal code. Data are periodically confirmed through a quality control process based on automatic filters (e.g. consistency among reported species, prevailing habitat, dive and observation depth) and manual procedures (e.g. matching between site name and geographic coordinates), and are then made freely accessible via an online geographic information system (Web GIS). Should the quality control process fail, meaning that issues are found with a given set of data, the volunteer(s) that has/have submitted such data is/are individually contacted in order to try to resolve the issue. Inconsistent data are permanently deleted only when this further step fails.

Reef Check Italia onlus - www.reefcheckmed.org - e-mail: postmaster@reefcheckitalia.it
Monitoraggio Ambiente Costiero
Coastal Environment Monitoring

Osservatore/Operator _____ Data/Date _____
 Località/Site _____ Prov. _____
 Lat. _____ ° Long. _____ °
 Orario/Hour _____ Tempo d'osservazione/Observation time _____ min
 Profondità osservazioni/Observation depth min _____ m, max _____ m, visibil. _____ m

Tipo fondale/Prevailing habitat _____
 A = 1 esemplare isolato/isolated specimen B = alcuni sparsi/some scattered C = molti sparsi/several scattered D = 1 area densa/1 crowded area E = alcune aree dense/some crowded areas F = molte aree dense/several crowded areas (drawings Cristina Giola Di Camillo)

<p>Caulerpa taxifolia</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth 1 A 2 B min _____ 3-5 C 6-10 D max _____ 11-50 E >50 F</p>	
<p>Axinella spp.</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth 1 2 min _____ 3-5 6-10 max _____ 11-50 >50</p>	
<p>Geodia cydonium</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth 1 2 min _____ 3-5 6-10 max _____ 11-50 >50</p>	
<p>Corallium rubrum</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth A B min _____ C D max _____ E F</p>	
<p>Eunicella cavolini</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth 1 2 min _____ 3-5 6-10 max _____ 11-50 >50</p>	
<p>Maasella edwardsi</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth A B min _____ C D max _____ E F</p>	
<p>Parazoanthus axinellae</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth A B min _____ C D max _____ E F</p>	
<p>Balanophyllia europaea</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth 1 2 min _____ 3-5 6-10 max _____ 11-50 >50</p>	
<p>Leptopsammia pruvoti</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth 1 2 min _____ 3-5 6-10 max _____ 11-50 >50</p>	
<p>Pinnaculus nobilis</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth 1 2 min _____ 3-5 6-10 max _____ 11-50 >50</p>	
<p>Homarus gammarus</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth 1 2 min _____ 3-5 6-10 max _____ 11-50 >50</p>	
<p>Scyllarides latus</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth 1 2 min _____ 3-5 6-10 max _____ 11-50 >50</p>	
<p>Hippocampus spp.</p> <p>0 Prof./Depth 1 2 min _____ 3-5 6-10 max _____ 11-50 >50</p>	

Fig. 3.22 Reef Check Med underwater plastic slate, back and front view (source: www.reefcheckmed.org)

Since 2006, trained scuba diver volunteers are collecting data on the distribution and abundance of 43 easily identifiable selected key marine species along the coasts of the Mediterranean Sea (Fig. 3.23).

Fig. 3.23 Observation made by RC Med volunteers (source: www.reefcheckmed.org)

The request of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC) to assess the environmental status of coastal areas threatened by multiple stressors (Micheli et al. 2013), and the broad availability of data collected by RCMed volunteers along subtidal rocky habitats suggest the possibility to develop innovative and reliable indices based on RCMed project (Turicchia et al. submitted). That may support decision-makers in planning and applying conservation strategies, especially in Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).

The Reef Check Mediterranean Species Sensitivity (*MedSens*) index is based on these species' distribution data and the sensitivities of the selected species toward physical, chemical and biological pressures, as indicated by the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC). Species sensitivities were assessed taking into account both the resistance and resilience of the selected species against each considered pressure, which are defined according to benchmark levels and detailed literature review.

MedSens index, easily calculated on open access data in each area and period of interest, provides the mean sensitivity of the surveyed assemblages, helping to assess the environmental quality status and to identify the most likely disturbs acting in the study area. Thanks to *MedSens*, the MCS can provide a useful tool to support decision makers to take marine biodiversity conservation measures (Turicchia et al. submitted).

As example, the *MedSens_{tot}* index was calculated for the management zones of Tavolara Capo Coda Cavallo MPA, Capo Gallo Femmine Island MPA, Tremiti Islands MPA and Tegnùe of Chioggia No-Take Zone (NTZ) (Fig. 3.24). Tavolara Capo Coda Cavallo MPA showed very high sensitive assemblages at zone B and moderate sensitivity at zone A (Fig. 3.24A). The assemblages living in the northern Adriatic coralligenous outcrops, included in the Tegnùe of Chioggia NTZ, are **among the least sensitive** of those found in Mediterranean protected areas (Fig. 3.24B). The Capo Gallo Femmine Island MPA presents moderate sensitivity of the assemblages (Fig. 3.24C), while the Tremiti Islands moderate sensitivity at zone C and very low sensitivity at zone B (Fig. 3.24D).

Fig. 3.24 Overall sensitivity assessment of assemblages (RC MedSens_{tot} Index) living in Tavolara Capo Coda Cavallo MPA (A), Tegnùe of Chioggia NTZ (B), Capo Gallo Femmine Island MPA (C) and Tremiti Islands MPA (D). Circled letters indicate the level of protection in the management zone (Mercator projection, WGS84 datum; Turicchia et al. submitted).

As a second example, based on the available data, it was possible to apply the *MedSens* index to a finer scale and to calculate the index for 12 out of 19 monitoring zones in the Portofino MPA (Fig. 3.25). According to the *MedSens_{tot}* index results, the assessed monitoring zones range from assemblages with very high sensitivity to assemblages with low sensitivity (Fig. 3.25A). The *MedSens* index shows to discriminate well among the different source of disturbance pressures: toward the physical disturbs (Fig. 3.25B), the chemical (Fig. 3.25C) and the biological disturbs (Fig. 3.25D)

Fig. 3.25 RC *MedSens* index applied on Portofino MPA monitoring zones towards the overall and the different source of disturbances: overall sensitivity of assemblages (A), sensitivity of assemblages towards physical disturbs (B), sensitivity of assemblages towards chemical disturbs (C) and sensitivity of assemblages towards biological disturbs (D) (Mercator projection, WGS84 datum; Turicchia et al. submitted).

MedSens index allows highlighting the areas that require management interventions, having the chance to assess the environmental quality status of coastal marine habitats at a finer scale and to identify the most likely disturbances acting in the study area.

Furthermore, the need of many independent observations, in order to apply the indices in the selected zones and in time, may represent the occasion to raise public awareness and enhance the collaboration between coastal management authorities (e.g., MPA managers), dive centres (i.e. stakeholders) and researchers, through a participatory approach. The U-CEM protocol and the application of the RC *MedSens* index thus provide an effective strategy to achieve the objectives set by the European Union (Turicchia et al. submitted).

CASE STUDY: Tavolara LAB project

The Marine Protected Areas play an important role not only in environmental conservation but also in raising citizens' awareness of environmental issues. According to Giakoumi et al. 2018, the main characteristics that determine efficient MPA management are high levels of stakeholder participation, strong social network/communication, explicit objectives, leadership and supporting legislation.

The MPA Tavolara Punta Coda Cavallo (Sardinia Island, Italy) represents an example of successful MPA in Italy. For several years the MPA has been organizing and supporting CS actions that led to the realization of the Tavolara LAB project. The project is aimed at promoting and spreading the biodiversity of the MPA Tavolara Punta Coda Cavallo through the involvement of civil society with CS projects. Tavolara LAB is a project shared and financed by the Italian Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare and accomplished in collaboration with the non-profit organization Reef Check Italia.

The project involved citizens, tourists and students in various actions:

- the Foresta sottomarina (Underwater forest) protocol for monitoring the *Posidonia oceanica* meadows (Fig. 3.26)

Fig. 3.26 Volunteers while monitoring the *Posidonia oceanica* at the MPA Tavolara Punta Coda Cavallo (source: www.amptavolara.it, Tavolara LAB)

- the Riconosci la Cernia (Recognize the grouper) protocol for the identification of the brown grouper, to monitor reproductive behaviour and migrations
- the Aliens protocol to recognize and report the non –indigenous marine species
- the activity Liberiamo le Dune (Free the dunes), for the eradication of the invasive plant *Carpobrotus* spp.
- the Spiaggia pulita (Clean beach) action for monitoring, through the Reef Check Med - Beach monitoring protocol, and cleaning the MPA beaches (Fig. 3.27)

Fig. 3.27 Students after taking part to the beach monitoring at MPA Tavolara Punta Coda Cavallo (source: www.amptavolara.it, Tavolara LAB)

The MPA also developed best practices for MPA's beaches entitled "Use the beach well - just 3 minutes of your attention for a more sustainable vacation" (Fig. 3.28).

USA BENE LA SPIAGGIA

Solo 3 minuti della tua attenzione per una vacanza più sostenibile.

È un'azione dedicata alla tutela degli ambienti costieri all'interno del progetto di scienza del cittadino dell'Area Marina Protetta Tavolara Punta Coda Cavallo, TavolaraLab, finanziato dal Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare e realizzato in collaborazione con l'associazione Reef Check Italia Onlus. **Tutti possiamo partecipare** scegliendo di comportarci in maniera più sostenibile. Come indicato nelle ordinanze sindacali dei tre Comuni che ospitano l'Area Protetta (Olbia, Loiri Porto San Paolo e San Teodoro),

ti invitiamo a fare più attenzione ai tuoi gesti quotidiani iniziando a rispettare queste semplici regole

1

Riduci i rifiuti che produci con piccoli accorgimenti e non abbandonarli nella natura, si trasformano in trappole mortali per gli animali e sporcano.

2

Se fumi, consulta le ordinanze comunali e porta sempre con te un posacenere.

3

Non raccogliere piante e fiori e non disturbare gli animali. Se sarai silenzioso potrai godere meglio della natura che ti circonda.

4

Non portare via sabbia, sassi e conchiglie. È un reato e i sassi e le conchiglie sono la spiaggia di domani.

5

Rispetta la Posidonia, sia viva che morta; è una pianta marina, non un'alga e protegge la spiaggia dall'erosione. È meglio una spiaggia che odora un pò che una che non c'è più.

6

Cammina sui percorsi tracciati e non oltrepassare le staccionate. Così non danneggi le dune e la vegetazione.

7

All'interno dell'area protetta informati sulle regole, anche attraverso il servizio del punto informativo sull'isola di Tavolara e rispettale; ricordati che anche un piccolo gesto, che ti sembra innocuo, se compiuto da tante persone può generare un problema.

Se vuoi partecipare alle attività educative e di sensibilizzazione
Consorzio di Gestione Area Marina Protetta di Tavolara Punta Coda Cavallo
T. 0789.203013 | info@amptavolara.it | www.amptavolara.it

Fig. 3.28 Best practices for visiting Tavolara Punta Coda Cavallo MPA's beaches (source: www.amptavolara.it, Tavolara LAB)

CASE STUDY: Ocean Conservancy - International Coastal Cleanup

Ocean Conservancy (www.oceanconservancy.org), founded as The Delta Corporation in 1972, is a non-profit environmental advocacy group based in Washington, D.C., United States. The Ocean Conservancy's mission is working with people to protect the ocean from today's greatest global challenges and to create science-based solutions for a healthy ocean and the wildlife and communities that depend on it. Through several programs, Ocean Conservancy advocates for protecting marine habitats, restoring sustainable fisheries and reducing the human impact on ocean ecosystems. One of the Ocean Conservancy's concerns involves setting up ocean cleanups, an event where volunteers can gather to remove trash from their local oceans (included in the program Fighting for Trash Free Seas®). Their main event is the International Coastal Cleanup (www.oceanconservancy.org/trash-free-seas/international-coastal-cleanup/), a day where nearly 12 million volunteers from 153 countries gather to clean up beaches and oceans throughout the world (Fig. 3.29). The movement was created by Linda Maraniss and Kathy O'Hara in 1986 when they organized the Ocean Conservancy's first local cleanup event. Since this first cleanup, Ocean Conservancy has helped to pick up over 140000 tons of trash from the beaches.

Fig. 3.29 Year 2018 International Coastal Cleanup (source: www.oceanconservancy.org)

To easily track the trash being picked up, Ocean Conservancy launched an app called Clean Swell in 2015 (Fig. 3.30). The user is allowed to log and photograph the trash they pick up and the information is then sent to the Ocean Conservancy's global trash database.

Fig. 3.30 Clean Swell App instruction (source: www.oceanconservancy.org)

Ocean Conservancy also provides information on the plastic problem for education and outreach purposes or suggest to take the pledge for other initiatives related to this topic (Fig. 3.31).

Fig. 3.31 Left: infographic on how plastic affects the marine environment; Right: poster of the “I skip the straw” campaign (source: www.oceanconservancy.org)

CASE STUDY: Ocean Conservancy – Good Mate

Ocean Conservancy’s Good Mate program outlines best boating practices (www.oceanconservancy.org/trash-free-seas/boating-community/; Fig. 3.32). While the program’s primary goal is to help recreational boaters and marina staff gain a better understanding and awareness of how they can help protect waterways while enjoying their recreational boating activities.

The long-term objectives of the Good Mate program are:

- Helping boaters and marinas develop and incorporate environmentally friendly management strategies in six areas: oil and fuel, sewage pollution, vessel maintenance and repair, marine debris, storm water runoff, and vessel operation
- Empowering boaters and marinas to take action against marine debris, by providing resources and support for watercraft and marina cleanups
- Educating and training recreational boaters and marina staff to be informed and educated stewards of waterways
- Helping boaters and marinas realize economic benefits while promoting environmentally friendly procedures
- Fostering cooperation between groups interested in the use, quality and enjoyment of local waters
- Keeping boating fun by maintaining a safe, pleasant and clean environment

Fig. 3.32 Infographic on the “Good Mate” program (source: www.oceanconservancy.org)

Unfortunately, mishandling a boat can harm ecosystems, wildlife and water quality. Improper handling, irresponsible or neglectful vessel maintenance, and poor refuelling, repair and storage habits all present environmental risks. Reducing these risks not only helps preserve clean water and protect the animals that live in it, but also keeps boaters and their families safe – and could even save them money.

While marinas are vital to the boating industry and the economy, the very nature of their business makes them a potential source for some of the most damaging types of water pollution. Fortunately, marina owners are in a unique position to stop trash and other pollution from entering the water. Incorporating green boating practices at your marina is good for the business and the environment.

Following, the best practices, the Ocean Conservancy Good Mate program suggest www.oceanconservancy.org/trash-free-seas/boating-community/boating/#oil).

Oil and fuel

- Refuelling is when most spills happen. The U.S. Coast Guard recommends filling the tank only 90 % to capacity to reduce the chance of spills from overfilling
- Even small oil spills spell trouble for water quality; bilge pumps can often discharge oil directly into the water. Use oil absorbent pads in the bilges of all boats with inboard engines
- Inspect thru-hull fittings often. A sinking boat is not only a safety risk for passengers but also leaks dangerous fuel, oil and chemicals into the water
- DO NOT use soaps to disperse spills – it is ILLEGAL

Sewage pollution

- Install and use a marine sanitation device as required by law
- Sewage and chemicals from holding tanks readily contaminate water; patronize marinas that offer pump-out services
- Bring portable toilets ashore for proper disposal

Vessel and maintenance repair

- Use non-hazardous materials - if it's hazardous to you, it's hazardous to the environment
- Old batteries can leach dangerous lead or cadmium, and expired marine flares contain toxic materials, too, so dispose of them properly
- When you paint your hull, choose products that are less dangerous to the environment than others

Marine debris

- Bring your food containers, cigarette butts and other trash back to shore and recycle when possible
- Let your marina know if it can provide better waste collection facilities
- Boaters are known for being good stewards and routinely picking up trash. For greater impact, raise awareness and collect data on what's out there by participating in Ocean Conservancy's International Coastal Cleanup

Stormwater runoff

- Use non-toxic cleaning products
- Discard worn motor parts carefully so the oil doesn't wash from them into storm drains
- Dispose of trash properly in onshore bins

Vessel operation

- *Anchors aweigh:* Choose anchor sites carefully and use proper techniques to avoid damaging sensitive habitat
- Avoid boating in shallow water, where you can stir up sediments and disturb underwater habitat - not to mention damage your propeller, hull and engine if you run aground
- Know where to go slow to prevent shore-damaging wakes

4. Code of Conduct

The development of a code of practices for tourists and tour operators is typically one of the first industry initiatives on the path of sustainable development in the form of codes of conduct and guidelines (Duff 1993, Wearing and Neil 2009). Ecological certification and labelling are among the most critical issues in the tourism sector. Around the world, there are a few hundred voluntary initiatives, including codes of conduct on tourism, labels, awards, benchmarking, and best practices (Wearing and Neil 2009). Certification is a voluntary procedure that evaluates, monitors and guarantees that a company, product, process, service or management system complies with specific requirements. It assigns a marketable logo or seal to those who meet or exceed basic standards to indicate socially and / or ecologically superior tourism practices (Wearing and Neil 2009). While eco-labelling describes a scheme in which a product or service may be awarded an ecological label based on its acceptable level of environmental impact. This acceptable level of environmental impact can be determined by taking into account of a single environmental disturbance or after undertaking an assessment of its overall impacts.

There are a number of examples of codes of conduct for marine ecotourism developed by the industry or industry associations. Just a few examples are the International Association of Antarctica Tour Operators' (IAATO) guidelines (www.iaato.org/visiting-antarctica/visitor-guidelines-library/, Fig. 4.1); the Code of Ethics for Whale Watchers developed by marine tour operators in the Bay of Fundy, Canada/USA (www.gmwsrs.org/Code%20of%20Ethics.pdf, Fig. 4.2) and the Sea Kayak Operators Association of New Zealand's code of practice for commercial

sea kayaking (www.supportadventure.co.nz/assets/Uploads/Seakayak-SKOANZ-COP-2011.pdf); and the Good Environmental Practices Snorkelling developed by the Coral Reef Alliance (CORAL) and Project Aware (Fig. 4.3).

Reducing Waste – Guidelines for Visitors to Antarctica

Be part of the solution

When travelling to Antarctica, there are steps you can take to reduce the amount of plastic and other waste produced. Waste is removed from Antarctica by ship or air and taken to ports outside the region for disposal, but these may have limited facilities depending on their location.

Your operator is working towards reducing single-use plastic in its operations. You could support their efforts and help leave no lasting signs of your visit by reducing the number of disposable items you bring, use and dispose of during your trip. There are also steps you can take to stop litter and harmful plastics from ending up in the environment.

Before traveling

- Travel with reusable items such as water bottle, coffee cup, reusable bag, reusable cutlery, etc. that you can bring home with you.
- Consider bringing a reusable waterproof bag to protect your camera from the elements.
- When packing toiletries, choose eco-friendly alternatives such as cosmetics free of microbeads.
- Choose products with non-plastic packaging such as soap and shampoo bars. Your accommodation may also be equipped with refillable dispensers. If you need to use plastic bottles and containers, use reusable ones.
- Synthetic clothing sheds small plastic fibers. We recognize that it may not be possible to entirely stop using synthetic clothing but reducing the amount we use is a great first goal.

When traveling

- When possible, avoid using disposable cups, straws, bottles, food containers and other items.
- Do not throw any non-organic items in the toilet, including wet wipes.
- Make sure all your belongings are well secured when outside. A moment of inattention and a gust of wind can easily blow light bags and other items away.
- Enquire about local environmental initiatives and how you can reduce your plastic footprint to support the community you visit.
- Talk to other travelers and staff – not everyone has the same experience and knowledge, so it is a good opportunity to learn from and inspire others.

Continue at home

- Reduce:** By consuming less and using reusable items you can help reduce the total amount of waste.
- Reuse:** Extend the life of your belongings. If you no longer need it, give it away.
- Recycle:** Learn about the cycle of your waste at home and sort out your waste accordingly to maximize the chances of material recovery.

Special note

Products labelled as 'degradable' or 'biodegradable' will degrade faster than regular plastic items but may still contain fossil fuels, thus creating microplastic particles. To effectively reduce waste, avoid using these alternative options and choose reusable items instead.

Please help keep these out of nature

	Cigarette butts because the filters contain plastic.
	Chewing gum because most gum is synthetic.
	Eye contact lenses because they are made of plastic.
	Paper cups because they are lined with plastic to remain waterproof.
	Tea bags because most are sealed with plastic glue.
	Wet wipes because they contain plastic fibers.

What the travel industry is doing

The International Association of Antarctica Tour Operators (IAATO) and the Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators (AECO) have joined the United Nations Clean Seas campaign. Together with their members, they are working to systematically reduce the use of disposable plastics and other items. Operators are also involving guests in beach cleanups worldwide and remove tons of marine litter every year. Through information to crew, staff and guests, and through sharing of best practices IAATO and AECO are involved in raising awareness and involvement in safeguarding of the environment, at sea and on land.

Are you an Antarctic Ambassador?

Join the conversation:

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To learn more about visiting Antarctica responsibly, please visit www.iaato.org

Fig. 4.1 International Association of Antarctica Tour Operators' guidelines (source: www.iaato.org)

CODE of ETHICS for Bay of Fundy Water-based Tour Operators

The purpose of this code is to foster an environment of co-operation and trust among water-based tour operators for the protection and safety of the whales and other marine wildlife, and the safety and understanding of their passengers. Tour operators agree to abide by this code for the protection and preservation of whales and the marine environment, and the education of their passengers and other boat operators. Adherence to this code demonstrates care and concern for whale conservation. **It is highly recommended that private individuals also abide by this code when watching whales.**

Definitions: A **vessel** will be defined as either a motorised vessel or a kayak group. A **kayak group** is defined as no more than 10 kayaks paddling in a co-ordinated group.

- The first vessel to locate a whale or group of whales will have first viewing priority. The vessel is under no obligation to announce the location of the whales to other operators.
- No more than two vessels will view a whale or group of whales at a time within 100m of the whale or group. If the whales are travelling, the viewing vessels will maintain a respectable distance to avoid herding the animals.
- A maximum of 30 minutes will be spent viewing a whale or group of whales if more than two vessels are in the immediate vicinity. Passengers will be informed that we are moving off to allow other vessels to view the whale and that we must avoid crowding the animals and endangering their safety. Motorised vessels will also take care not to crowd or endanger the safety of kayakers.
- Any whale showing avoidance behaviour such as turning away or increasing speed will be left alone.
- All operators will stand-by on a designated VHF radio channel for purposes of communication when one vessel is viewing or waiting to view a more than whale or group of whales, and we will co-ordinate the selection of the channel with whale watch vessels from other areas in the Bay of Fundy.
- Vessels approaching another vessel already engaged in whale watching will contact that vessel and arrange viewing priority.
- A fair distance will be kept when waiting to view so as not to crowd the whale or viewing vessels. While waiting tour operators will engage in other activities such as sea bird and seal viewing, or conservation education.
- When vessels are stopping to listen for whale blows in the fog, as a courtesy other vessels in the immediate vicinity will do the same.
- Vessels will cover different areas as much as possible so that not all vessels will be converging on the same location.
- In the vicinity of fixed fishing gear whales will not be herded in the direction of the gear.

GRAND MANAN WHALE & SEABIRD RESEARCH STATION
24 Route 776
Grand Manan, NB Canada E5G 1A1
Telephone (506) 662 3804 Website www.gmwrs.org

Fig. 4.2 Code of Ethics for Whale Watchers (source: www.gmwrs.org)

GOOD ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES
SNORKELING

Coral reefs are among the world's most spectacular ecosystems and snorkeling is an excellent way to explore them. As coral reefs face an increasingly uncertain future, snorkelers and other coral reef visitors can play an important role in helping protect these fragile habitats. Follow these simple guidelines to become a "coral friendly" snorkeler.

BEFORE SETTING OUT TO EXPLORE THE REEFS

- For your vacation, choose an environmentally friendly resort or hotel; one that practices energy conservation, recycles, and treats sewage and solid waste in responsible ways.
- Pay user fees or make a donation when visiting coral parks and other marine conservation areas.
- Get the best possible snorkeling instruction you can.
- Practice snorkeling skills away from the reef.
- Make sure your equipment fits properly before you snorkel near corals—it can be very difficult to adjust in the water.
- If you feel uncertain, or are an inexperienced snorkeler, consider wearing a snorkel vest for added buoyancy.
- Learn all you can about coral reefs—they are fascinating and fragile environments.

IN THE WATER

- Never touch corals; even slight contact can harm them. Some corals can sting or cut you.
- Select points of entry and exit to avoid walking on corals.
- Maintain a comfortable distance from the reef, so as to avoid contact.
- Know where your fins are at all times and don't kick up sand.
- Stay horizontal in the water while you're near or above the reef.
- Learn to swim without using your arms.
- Take nothing living or dead out of the water except recent garbage which does not have living organisms on it.
- Move slowly and deliberately in the water—relax as you swim and take your time.
- Avoid using gloves in coral environments.
- Remember, look but don't touch.

Good snorkelers know that the best way to enjoy a reef is to slow down, relax and watch as reef creatures go about their daily lives undisturbed.

Be sure to find out about local laws and regulations as they may differ from these general guidelines.

GOOD ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES
SNORKELING

MINIMIZE CONTACT WITH MARINE LIFE

- Never chase, harass or try to ride marine life.
- Never touch or handle marine life.

ON BOATS

- Choose snorkel operations whose boats make use of available moorings—anchors and chains destroy fragile corals.
- Make sure garbage is well stowed, especially light plastic items.
- Be sure to take away everything you brought on board, such as packaging, used batteries and bottles.

SHORESIDE

- Support coral parks and other conservation projects:
 - Visit established coral parks and pay applicable user fees that support marine conservation.
 - Encourage and support the use of boat moorings.
 - Participate in local initiatives to monitor the marine environment.
 - Participate in cleanups.
 - Make a donation or volunteer your skills to support a coral park. For example, you can participate in a reef survey, conduct outreach, or help educate others about reef conservation.
 - Donate used equipment such as cameras, dive gear or reef identification books.
- Avoid purchasing souvenirs made from coral, turtles or other marine life—this is often illegal, and it's never environmentally wise.
- Speak up. Make sure your snorkeling buddies understand these simple but important conservation practices.

The Coral Reef Alliance (CORAL) is a member-supported, non-profit international organization dedicated to keeping coral reefs alive around the world. Visit our website <http://www.coral.org>

Visit the Project AWARE Foundation website at www.projectaware.org to find out more about protecting the aquatic environment and its resources.

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Fig. 4.3 Good Environmental practices for snorkelling (source: CORAL and Project AWARE)

Adherence to the guidelines can provide a sustainable tourism experience but it will not in itself constitute an ecotourism experience unless there is an element of education and interpretation during the visit (Cater and Cater 2007 and reference therein).

4.1 Sustainable practices for on-the-water tourism activities

Code of conducts for recreational and operational boat

Recommendation for boating practices and disposal:

- Provide adequate garbage facilities on board vessel and briefing your guest about them
- Adopt “responsible garbage” policies (e.g. use eco-friendly cleaning products, provide recycle bins on the boat, ensure that no litter goes in the sea). Include information about these during the boat briefing
- Take all litter (for example, rubbish, food scraps and cigarette butts) with you and responsibly dispose of it on shore
- Collect litter that you find in the water, and ashore
- Ensure that no trash is discarded, washed or blow overboard
- Report all oil and fuel spills and suspected illegal disposal of wastes
- Refuel onshore where possible, using the correct gear and have clean-up equipment ready
- Prevent overfilling fuel tanks (e.g. use a rag to cover the air vent during fueling)
- Open the waste water tank off the coast and leave it closed when in port

-
- Provide guests with information on local Marine National Park, environmental rules and regulation
 - Participate in and promote beach cleanup, especially in areas that are only accessible by boat (share these activities on your social media and website)
 - Be considerate of others when motoring or anchoring near them
 - Participate in the development and implementation of mooring buoy program, if available

Recommendation around wild marine animals (e.g. turtles, monk seals and dolphins):

- Never touch, grab or lean on marine animals
- Do not try to feed marine animals
- Report entangled, stranded or dead marine animals
- Be on the lookout for surfacing turtles or monk seals. Travel slowly in these cases, with no wake
- If a marine animal is close to your vessel, engage neutral and allow the animal to move freely
- Do not encircle or trap marine animal with vessels. Allow an escape route
- Do not drive your vessel over a marine animal
- Do not pursue marine animal if they try to avoid the vessel or flee the area.
- Do not intentionally drive through a pod of dolphins to try to get them to bow-ride – some dolphins don't bow ride, and can become disturbed near boats
- If you do come across dolphins bow riding, maintain a constant speed and direction.
- Avoid making sudden noise, speed or direction changes

Recommendation for marine caves and beach visit:

- Be aware that marine cave are extremely fragile marine environments
- Briefing your guests about the natural environmental importance they are visiting and how to conduct to preserve them (e.g. do not leave trash inside the cave, do not touch, do not stand on underwater rock, do not collect sea shells)
- If possible, do not enter into the cave with your boat
- If enter the cave, be careful do not touch the wall and to put the engine in neutral
- Encourage snorkeling inside the cave rather than entering by boat
- Implement the register of users on the sites, ensuring a shift between all operators. This is could be done through the use of new technologies, such as a dedicated smartphone app.
- It could be useful to implement a regulation on the entrance to the caves
- Diversify your itinerary to find less crowded spot and to ensure a more natural experience to your guests
- Do not leave trash on the beach
- For a better natural experience, keep the music at a not too loud volume

Recommendation for anchoring:

- Use public moorings where available and do not anchor within no-anchoring areas
- Where possible, anchor in sand or mud away from seagrass and other fragile marine environments. Suitable areas often show up as flat and smooth on your sounder.
- Anchor a safe distance from other boats and look out for people in the water when dropping your anchor.
- If anchoring ashore, carefully place the anchor to minimize damage.
- Carry enough chain and line for the depth you want to anchor in and use only as much chain as you need to hold the vessel safely.
- Do not force the anchor free by motoring forward.
- Keep watch to make sure the anchor isn't dragging
- Please report any misused or damaged moorings.

Recommendation for using public moorings:

- It could be useful to set a time limits for using public moorings or pontoons
- As a user, if the time limit is set, do not exceed it
- Do not attach more vessel than those allowed to a public mooring
- Do not raft-up – attach multiple vessels in a chain when one vessel is attached to the mooring
- Do not alter the mooring
- Follow the instructions on the mooring (Fig. 4.4)
- Train your boat skippers and staff in regard to correct mooring and driving safety procedures.
- Provide more stringent surveillance and policing of mooring / anchoring offences
- In case of founding a damaged mooring, please make a note of any markings and its GPS position so it can be reported
- In case of founding an adrift buoy, report it

Fig. 4.4 Buoys delimiting the K-S MPA (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Recommendation during vessel maintenance:

- Choose an approved slipway and maintenance facility, where possible. Contain any water used in the cleaning process that may be contaminated
- Use non-toxic, phosphate-free, chlorine-free cleaners (for example, baking soda, vinegar, citrus-based products, vegetable-based soaps or look for “phosphate-free” and “biodegradable” on the product label). Avoid cleaners with bleach, ammonia, lye or petroleum distillates
- Use cleaning and degreasing chemicals sparingly
- Use non-toxic antifouling alternatives, if practical (for example, silicon-based coatings, two-pack epoxy paint)
- Wash your vessel down occasionally with a soft cloth to remove the slime layer and prevent the build-up of secondary fouling
- Inspect the hull of your vessel regularly - as well as the internal seawater pipe work, fenders, anchors, open bilges, propellers and sea chests - for marine growth
- Dispose the waste according to the regulation
- Keep your outboard engines in good condition, fix all leaks as soon as possible
- Dispose of fuel rag at a hazardous waste facility, not in the rubbish bin

Recommendation for outboard engines:

Many outboard small engines, such as conventional two-stroke engines used in marine outboard and personal watercraft, are high polluters relative to their engine size and usage, emitting a range of toxins into the water and the air.

- Consider purchasing a new, cleaner marine engine (i.e. four-stroke is better than a two-stroke engines)
- Consider purchasing an electric motor
- Ensure that your outboard motor is kept in good condition and serviced according to the manufacturer's recommendations (e.g. Fig. 4.5)
- Properly match engine horsepower to the size of your vessel
- Use the right size propeller and keep it in good condition
- Drive your boat conservatively. Abrupt starts and excessive speed not only reduce fuel efficiency and increase emissions, but are also dangerous for slow-moving marine animals such as turtles
- Learn to trim your boat whilst underway
- Reduce weight

BEST PRACTICES FOR BOATERS

Fig. 4.5 Best environmental practices for boats with graphic examples of what to do and what not to do

Code of conducts for diving and snorkeling

Recommendation for diving and snorkeling operator and staff:

- Train yourself about the marine protected species present in your diving area
- Train your staff and educate your guests about the potential negative impact that humans can have on the marine environment
- Raise public awareness on environment conservation. The more the guests know about the marine life, the more they will want to conserve it
- Host and participate in underwater and beach cleanups with your community and guests
- Host, participate and promote Citizen Science initiatives (e.g. monitoring)
- Provide briefing for employees and guests regarding good environmental practices for marine recreational activities (i.e. diving and snorkeling) and about marine environment
- A standard audio-visual dive briefing presentation could be developed for use by all operators. The presentation should provide insights into the unique diving experiences, and in an informative manner educate divers towards appropriate dive behavior
- Provide guests with information on local Marine National Park, environmental rules and regulation

-
- an eye-catching and informative poster should be developed that instructs divers and snorkelers to proper behavior. It should also be distributed, perhaps in laminated form, not only to dive centers, but also to snorkel charter boat operators and hotels
 - Adopt “responsible garbage” policies (e.g. use eco-friendly cleaning products, provide recycle bins on the boat, ensure that no litter goes in the sea). Include information about these during the boat briefing
 - Properly dispose engines oil and batteries
 - Be a role model (e.g. no touch marine life, collect trash underwater, make responsible seafood choices)
 - Reinforce good diving behavior by promoting good buoyancy, marine biology and monitoring course
 - Help your diver guests to improve their buoyancy, swimming position and finning techniques during the dive
 - Promote a “no touch” policy for all the diving. Correct your guests if they touch or chase marine life
 - Ensure that all your guests dive equipment is secured
 - Discourage the purchase of marine organisms
 - Ensure inexperienced swimmers wear life jacket when snorkeling
 - Bring a spear life jacketed when you lead a snorkeling tour
 - A good diving ratio could be 1 guide to 4 divers (with this ratio all of your guests are in your range of vision in case of
-

accidental contact with marine life dangling equipment and an emergency situation)

- Avoid single use plastic on boat (e.g. plastic bottles, plastic cups)
- Run your boat on the most fuel-efficient way
- Use mooring buoys whenever available
- Participate in the development and implementation of mooring buoy program, if available
- Implement operator use-roster at busy diving and snorkeling spots
- Report environmental violation

Recommendation for divers and snorkelers (Fig. 4.6):

- Respect the marine environment
- Enhance the quality of your dive experience by learning about the environment you'll visit
- Support and take part at initiatives aimed at the conservation of marine environment (e.g. Citizen science monitoring, beach or underwater cleanup)
- Asking about diving operator environmental best practices
- Wearing a wet suit or lycra suit when snorkeling or diving will help to protect you from the sun burn and stings from jellyfish
- Practice buoyancy control before approaching the rocky bottom - test buoyancy whenever you're using new equipment such as new wetsuits, buoyancy control devices (BCDs) and cameras
- Make sure you are properly weighted before diving
- Check that all your dive gear is secure before you get into the water so that it doesn't dangle and catch on the rocky bottom
- Move slowly and deliberately in the water, relax and take your time - avoid rapid changes in direction
- Avoid making sudden or loud noises underwater
- Avoid leaning on, holding onto or touching - this is particularly important when you are taking underwater photographs
- Avoid kicking up and stirring up sediment by keeping your distance (e.g. stay one meter from the bottom, when possible)
- Avoid touching any animals or plants. They can die and break easily under pressure

-
- Avoid feeding fish, it will disrupt their feeding habitats and behavior
 - Keep clear of free-swimming animals (such as turtles). In particular, do not chase, ride, grab or block the path of these animals
 - Avoid relocating any marine life, particularly when taking photos and filming
 - Do not collect marine species, such as seashell underwater or on the beach
 - Dispose your trash in the nearest bin. Do not litter in the sea
 - Use recycling bins correctly, when available
 - Bring your own reusable water bottle and avoid single use-plastics (e.g. plastic cups)
 - Collect trash on dive, if it safe
 - Make responsible seafood choice (e.g. do not eat endangered or protected marine species)
 - Be an eco-tourist, look for environmentally friendly dive centers

Recommendation for diving at maritime heritage sites (e.g. shipwreck):

- Do not anchor on shipwrecks
- Use moorings wherever possible
- Locate the wreck using a depth sounder, if it's unmarked
- Drop the anchor upwind, or up-current, of the wreck site and lay back on the anchor line until the boat is over the wreck
- Do not enter the wreck, instead observe from the outside
- Keep diving groups small
- Look but don't touch
- Ensure that all diving equipment are secured firmly and not dragging
- Be aware of your fins
- Exercise proper buoyancy control

Fig. 4.6 Best environmental practices for divers and snorkelers with graphic examples of what to do and what not to do

Code of conducts for recreational fishing

Recommendation for recreational fishing (Fig. 4.7):

- Comply with the fishing requirements in the Marine National Park Zoning Plan
- Comply with the national fishing regulations including species allowed, size limits, bag limits, protected species, tackle restrictions and seasonal and area closures
- Report suspected illegal fish kills, entrapped marine animals and suspected illegal fishing activity (e.g. the use of dynamite or fishing protected species)
- Avoid anchoring on sea grasses
- Take only what you need
- If you're unsure of the fish size, release the fish immediately
- Return all undersized and unwanted fish quickly to minimize injury
- If you're keeping the fish, remove it from the hook or net immediately and kill it humanely
- Use barbless hooks or those that are unlikely to become hooked in the gills or gut
- Do not litter - clean up all fishing gear (such as discarded tackle and line, and bait bags) and take it back to shore to dispose of it properly
- Avoid single use plastic on boat (e.g. plastic bottles, plastic cups)
- Run your boat on the most fuel-efficient way

Fig. 4.7 Best environmental practices for recreational fishing with graphic examples of what to do and what not to do

Recommendation for spearfishing:

- Comply with the fishing requirements in the Marine National Park Zoning Plan
- Comply with the national fishing regulations including species allowed, size limits, bag limits, protected species, tackle restrictions and seasonal and area closures
- Always track down injured fish, do not let them swim off injured
- Spear only what you need
- Do not pursue a fish if you are unsure of its identity or size
- Do not take big fish merely as trophies because these are important breeding stock
- When you spearfish, you cannot use a powerhead or other firearm, a light, scuba or other underwater breathing apparatus
- When you are out of the water, the spear guns cannot have a loaded spear gun
- When returning unwanted fish, minimize the length of time a fish is out of the water
- When returning unwanted fish, handle it gently (i.e. fully support its body, do not hold upright by the jaw, squeeze on the fish)
- When returning unwanted fish, to minimize damage to their protective mucous coating, use wet hands or cloth when handling it
- When returning unwanted fish, remove the hook carefully and quickly using a pair of long-nose pliers or a de-hooker. If the hook is difficult to remove, cut the line instead

Code of conducts for motorized water sports

Recommendation for motorized water sports, which include jet skiing, parasailing and waterskiing:

- Respect other users in the area, pay attention to noise and wakefulness
- Keep a safe distance from people in the water
- Look for marine animals such as dolphins and turtles: slow down and pay attention especially in areas where it is known to occur
- Proceed slowly near islands and bays, especially where sea birds nest or roost
- When travelling in shallow water, keep the watercraft at idle speed to minimize sediment stirring
- Avoid beaching or anchoring in sensitive areas such as seagrass beds
- Mount a propeller cover to protect wildlife

Code of conducts for waste, sewage and litter

Recommendations for bilge maintenance and cleaning:

- Use a drip pan under the engine to reduce leaks into the bilge
- Do not pump bilge water overboard if oil is present in the bilge
- Use oil absorbent pads or towels to remove oil from the bilge or other areas of the vessel. Do not use a degreasing compound
- Empty the bilge on shore to licensed waste disposal contractors, if the facilities are available
- Use enzyme-based bilge cleaners - do not use detergents, degreasers or chemicals

Recommendations for greywater and sewage:

- Use readily biodegradable and environmentally friendly chemicals for cleaning and maintenance
- When pump out greywater at sea, make sure you're as far away from the coast and islands as possible
- Use biodegradable toilet paper and phosphate-free cleaning products

Recommendation for spill response:

Have an adequate spill response kit onboard (Fig. 4.8)

Fig. 4.8 Example of spill response kit

Recommendation for marine litter:

- Do not throw garbage into the sea (such as leftover food, plastic, paper, fishing gear and cigarette butts), return it to shore for proper disposal
- Secure all loose articles, clothing and towels on the deck, to prevent them from blowing off or accidentally falling overboard
- Retrieve everything that has fallen overboard
- If possible, retrieve all entangled fishing gear
- Collect all litter from the water every time you see it
- Use reusable or biodegradable products (e.g. washable dishes and cloth napkins), where possible
- Minimize packaging and pre-packaged food

4.2 Ecotourism guidelines for travellers

As an eco-traveller, it is important and a responsibility to prevent or minimize any negative impact on the environment, the local community and the economy of the destination visited. For this reason, guidelines have also been drafted for travellers to maintain responsible behaviour, respect for the environment and the communities visited.

For example, in 2012 the Travel Care Code Workgroup has developed the Travel Care Code (www.travelcarecode.org/thecarecode) and issued the document Pledge to Travel Green with 10 ways to care for travellers (Fig. 4.9), which includes:

1. prepare for your trip: educate yourself about your destination; learn about local history, customs and culture as well as vital ecosystems; learn the basics of the local language; approach travel with the desire to learn rather than just observe
 2. respect local traditions and etiquette: appropriate clothing; be aware of people's sensitivity to being photographed; observe local customs; remember that you are the visitor; different concepts of time, personal space, communication
 3. avoid ostentatious display of wealth: extravagant to another culture; create barriers and inhibit genuine interactions
 4. be flexible in your expectations: adapt yourself to the situation rather than trying to adapt the situation to you
 5. conserve resources
 6. practice environmental minimum impact
 7. choosing a tour operator or guide
 8. support local economies
-

9. bridging cultural gaps
10. continued ecotourism

PLEDGE TO TRAVEL GREEN

UNITED STATES TRAVEL CARE CODE

-

1. Learn about Your Destination – Enjoy a rewarding experience by learning more about the natural environment, culture and history that make every destination unique.
-

2. Don't Leave Your Good Habits at Home – While traveling, continue to recycle; use water wisely, and turn off lights as you would at home.
-

3. Be a Fuel-Efficient Traveler – Book direct flights, rent smaller cars, and keep your own vehicle operating at maximum efficiency. Once in your destination, walk or bike as much as possible.
-

4. Make Informed Decisions – Seek out destinations or companies that engage in energy efficiency or recycling programs and that take actions to preserve their communities and natural environment.
-

5. Be a Good Guest – Remember that you are a guest in your destination. Engage with locals, but respect their privacy, traditions and local community.
-

6. Support Locals – As a visitor, the money you spend on your trip can help support the local artisans, farmers and business owners whose livelihoods depend on tourism.
-

7. Dispose of Your Waste Properly – Leave a beautiful place for others to enjoy. Recycle where possible, and always dispose of your waste with care.
-

8. Protect Your Natural Surroundings – Be mindful of the plants, animals and ecosystems that you impact. Avoid feeding wildlife; stay on designated trails, and strictly follow all fire restrictions.
-

9. Make Your Travel Zero Emissions – As an additional step, consider the option of purchasing carbon credits to fully offset your travel's impact on climate change.
-

10. Bring Your Experiences Home – Continue practicing your sustainable habits at home, and encourage friends and family to travel with the same care.

For more tips and resources on traveling with care – see: www.TravelCareCode.org

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 Developed and managed by the Center for Sustainable Tourism www.sustainabletourism.org

Fig. 4.9 Pledge to Travel Green brochures (www.travelcarecode.org)

4.3 Accrediting

A solution for the security and quality of the touristic experience can be the accreditation. It offers the chance to improve industry standards and to provide quality assurance in a highly competitive market. It can also enhance the protection of the natural environment, on which ecotourism depends, and guarantee suitable practices and more informed decision-making processes by ecotourists (Wearing and Neil 2009).

Accreditation involves a formal recognition of adherence to agreed standards. Quality assurance for both operators and tourists and the creation of competitive marketing advantages are benefits often associated with the accreditation. In the accreditation systems, through the identification and evaluation of a series of good environmental practice initiatives in the ecotourism sector, the tour operator integrates and adopts changes to its business (Wearing and Neil 2009 and reference therein).

CASE STUDY: Australia’s Nature & Ecotourism Accreditation Program

The world's first national ecotourism accreditation program was developed and launched by Australia's Ecotourism Association and the Australian Tourism Operator Network in 1996.

The Accreditation Program for Nature and Ecotourism in Australia (NEAP; www.ecotourism.org.au), having been one of the first specifically designed for ecotourism, is rapidly becoming a model for similar initiatives around the world, as well as the best-known certification program (Newson 2001, Wearing and Neil 2009). Nowadays, Ecotourism Australia has 500 members and over 1,700 certified products. The program is based on principles of ecologically sustainable development and offers operators the opportunity to be innovative and continuously improve their practices (Wearing and Neil 2009). There are three categories of accreditation: naturalistic tourism, ecotourism and advanced ecotourism (Fig. 4.10).

Australia's leading and most innovative ecotourism products that operate with minimal impact on the environment and provide opportunities to learn about the environment with operators who are committed to achieving best practice, using resources wisely, contributing to conserving the environment and helping local communities.

Tourism in a natural area that focuses on optimal resources use, leaves minimal impact on the environment and offers interesting ways to learn about the environment with operators that use resources wisely, contribute to conserving the environment and help local communities.

Tourism in natural areas that leaves minimal impact on the environment.

Fig. 4.10 Categories of accreditation for the Accreditation Program for Nature and Ecotourism in Australia (source: www.ecotourism.org.au/our-certification-programs/eco-certification/)

The application process initially involves the completion of the self-assessment in relation to the minimum standards. An appropriately qualified and appointed ecotourism accreditation assessor evaluates the self-assessment and forwards the application to the ecotourism accreditation committee for approval or rejection (Fig. 4.11).

Fig. 4.11 Application certification process (www.ecotourism.org.au/our-certification-programs/eco-certification/certification-process/)

The rigour of the certification procedure is illustrated by the fact that if an accredited company does not meet the criteria, its accreditation status can be suspended or revoked. For example, among the operators of maritime

tourism in the Great Barrier Reef National Park, one operator was suspended for certification, and 11 were invited to face minor violations. In addition, every 3 years, an external on-site audit checks each certified operation. The aim over time is to increase minimum standards on a regular basis and to ensure that best practices can be achieved on an ongoing basis (Wearing and Neil 2009).

CASE STUDY: The Blue Flag

The Blue Flag (www.blueflag.global) certification was created in France in 1985 as a pilot program of the Office of the Foundation for Environmental Education in Europe (FEE), where French coastal municipalities obtained the Blue Flag based on criteria relating to water treatment wastewater and the quality of bathing water. Its mission is to promote sustainability in the tourism sector through environmental education, environmental protection and other sustainable development practices.

The Blue Flag criteria ([/www.blueflag.global/criteria](http://www.blueflag.global/criteria)) include quality, safety, education and environmental information standards, service provision and general environmental management criteria. The beaches, marinas and operators of sustainable nautical tourism (since 2016, Fig. 4.12) require the Blue Flag as a symbol and indication of their high environmental and quality standards.

Sail Training International
BLUE FLAG SCHEME
CODE OF CONDUCT
(For sail training vessels)

The individual Blue Flag is awarded to the interested vessel owner/operator upon signing the following Code of Conduct:

- I will not throw garbage into the sea or along the coast.
- I will not discharge black water (sewage) holding tanks in coastal waters, sensitive sea areas or harbours. I will arrange to discharge my black water tanks in the reception facilities provided by the port authority or marina. (Vessels with holding tanks).
- I will not release toilet water in the sea in near coastal waters and sensitive areas. (Vessels without black water holding tanks).
- I will not release poisonous or toxic waste (oil, paint, used batteries, cleaning agents, etc) in the sea.
- I will deliver these types of waste to the containers at the appropriate reception facilities provided by the port authority or marina.
- I will undertake and promote recycling and the use of recycling facilities.
- I will use the most environmentally friendly products among paints, anti-foulings, paint remover, detergents, etc, that are available and work efficiently.
- I will report pollution or other violations of environmental regulations to the appropriate authorities.
- I will not engage in forbidden fishing practices and I will respect time periods when fishing is prohibited.
- I will protect animals and plants in the sea, including not disturbing breeding birds, seals or other marine animals.
- I will respect vulnerable and protected areas.
- I will avoid damage of the sea bottom, eg in the way that I anchor.
- I will avoid disturbing fishing activities or fishing gear.
- I will not buy or use objects made from protected species or from archaeological underwater findings.
- I will encourage other sailors also to take care of the environment.

Vessel name:

Signed (vessel owner):

Signed (Sail Training International representative):

Date:

The Sail Training International Blue Flag scheme for sail training vessel owners/operators is promoted and monitored by Sail Training International (www.sailtraininginternational.org) and the Foundation for Environmental Education (www.fee-international.org). Sail Training International and the Foundation for Environmental Education will maintain a register of all vessel owners/operators approved for the scheme.

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Fig. 4.12 Example of code of conduct from the Blue Flag scheme (source: www.blueflag.global)

As an example, here is a simplified list of the Blue Flag (Fig. 4.13) sustainable boating tourism operator criteria.

Environmental education and information

- Information to relevant local environmental phenomena, local ecosystems and sensitive areas in the surrounding environment
- Information about the Blue Flag programme
- Code of conduct for passengers which includes the adequate disposal of litter, smoking policy on board, safety measures and the proper behaviour during an encounter with wild animals
- At least one environmental education activity has to be offered within the operating season
- Environmental training for all employees
- Provision of a qualified guide on guided tours

Environmental management

- It is recommended to establish a management committee with responsibility for instituting environmental management systems and conducting regular environmental audits
 - Each tour operator has to have an environmental policy and an environmental plan
 - All regulations pertaining to the location and the operation of the boats have to be complied with
-

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- Use of adequate, properly identified and segregated containers for the storage of hazardous wastes
 - Use of adequate litter bins, including recycling bins
 - Correct disposal of all wastes produced by the tourists and the tour operator
 - Use of recyclable products, biodegradable materials and environmentally-friendly toiletries and cleaning products
 - Smoking should be prohibited on the boats
 - Correct treatment of bilge water
 - Provision of adequate sanitary facilities with correct sewage disposal
 - Repair and paintwork on the boats must be limited to specifically designated areas
 - Promotion of sustainable means of transportation from and to the boats
 - Report of accidents that might cause environmental damages
 - Speed and engine maintenance of the boats must be aimed at maximising energy efficiency and minimising pollution
 - Environmentally friendly anchoring
 - Correct disposal of boats that have reached the end of their life service

Safety and services

- Provision of adequate and well-signposted lifesaving, first-aid and fire-fighting equipment which has been approved by relevant national authorities
- Provision of emergency plans for different possible kinds of accidents and regular emergency trainings for the crew
- Safety precautions and information must be presented on the boat
- Facilities for people with disabilities should be in place
- Adequate signage indicating the location of the different facilities on the boats

Social responsibility

- Discrimination based on gender, sexual orientation, disabilities, origin or religious affiliation should not be accepted within the tour operator
- Payment of fair salaries according to the respective income level in the country
- The legal working age in the respective country should be respected
- The tour operator should support the local economy by choosing to buy and use local products

Responsible tourism

- Vulnerable and protected areas must be respected
- Any wildlife must be approached at a slow speed and in a manner that allows the animal(s) to evaluate the situation. They must not be encircled, trapped or chased
- Special precaution must be taken in the vicinity of breeding animals. Young animals must not be separated from their group
- When in the direct vicinity of any wildlife, noise must be reduced to a minimum and the engine should be put into neutral whenever appropriate
- No animals or plants are to be touched or collected
- Tourists and employees must not feed the animals
- If there are any signs of disturbance, the boat must increase its distance from the animals
- The tour operator should be open to cooperation with research institutions. The company's vessel might function as a research platform, and collected data of wildlife sightings should be made available to researchers
- Injured, entangled, stranded or dead animals must be reported to the local authorities

Fig. 4.13 Blue Flag (source: Roberta F., CC BY-SA 3.0, www.commons.wikimedia.org)

Furthermore, with concrete actions, the activities and partners that adhere to the Blue Flag contribute to pursuing the United Nations' sustainable development goals. In this context, for example, the Blue Flag helps protect underwater life (United Nations Sustainable Development Goals No. 14). Indeed, the Blue Flag program promotes the sustainable development of marine and freshwater areas. It causes local authorities, beach operators and operators of sustainable nautical tourism to achieve high standards of water quality, environmental management, environmental education and information, safety and services. Many of its initiatives concern the monitoring of the quality of bathing water, the conservation of biodiversity and the coastal ecosystem.

Following there are some examples of Blue Flag best practices.

In Portugal, on different beaches, the best practice concerns the reuse of plastic, transforming it into furniture and / or beach equipment, such as a

walkway on the sand, information panels, deck chairs, etc. It is more sustainable, has a longer life and less need for maintenance. Furthermore, it has been aesthetically treated to imitate wood.

In Canada, the Able Sail program allows access and navigation opportunities for people with physical or cognitive disabilities and improves their quality of life (www.burlbay.com/about-the-marina-2.php).

Also in Canada, in 2015, the city of Toronto launched its SwimSafe website and mobile app. Toronto's 11 beaches are monitored for *E. coli* every day from June to September. The app is an excellent resource for visitors and residents who want to know if their nearby beach is safe for swimming (www.toronto.ca/health/swimsafe/beaches_mobile.htm)

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